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0 Executive Summary

Aviation offers a mobility means to citizen. However, air traffic constant increase since a few decades and perspective of sustained growth in the future, induces environmental impacts on air quality and climate from aircraft emissions, mainly CO₂, NO_x and particles. This concern is particularly critical today, in the context of the COP21 climate objective and the increasing sensitivity on local air quality, in particular in Europe. Therefore, assuming that an accurate evaluation of these anthropogenic impacts is available, it is fundamental to develop appropriate technical mitigation solutions, which may be also encouraged by relevant international regulations. In that context, the Advisory Council for Aeronautic Research in Europe (ACARE), defined very challenging technological goals in terms of CO₂ and NO_x mitigation, and one should be able to measure how far we are from these goals.

Series of 15 focused workshops were organized all along the FORUM-AE project which ended in 2017, addressing these concerns in three thematic chapters : i) the scientific understanding of environmental impacts, ii) the identification of potentially promising technical and technological solutions, with an assessment of their expected benefits and maturity, iii) relevant regulation technical issues. Detailed results of all these workshops may be found in their respective proceedings available on the project's website (www.forum-ae.eu) and are synthesized in this document. The following gives a non exhaustive sample of key statements and recommendations, corresponding to the vision end 2017.

On air quality impact

- PM_{2.5} mass concentrations linked to airport activities appear most of the time to be small compared to contributions from other sources, and very small against air quality limits. UFP contributions from airport activities are of stronger concern with elevated number concentrations observed not only close to runways but also distances away from the airport. However, this should be consolidated with more airport studies.
- Aircraft cruise emissions might impact ground air quality. Little modelling effort on this topic is currently performed in Europe. It appears that NO_x and SO_x emitted in cruise by the aircraft engines have a dominant contribution to ground PM_{2.5} whereas nvPM cruise emissions are more marginal. However, estimation of uncertainties associated to the predicted levels is strongly needed.

On climate Impact

- Choosing an adequate climate impact metric is still an open key issue. Relating to the strategic climate policy 2°C goal as spelled out by COP21, an associated metric is required, for providing guidance in the way to achieve it. Additionally, a need becomes apparent for a metric which reflects the long-term climate impact.
- **Climate-optimised flight routing** must be further developed, ideally considering the **individual weather situation**. Using climate change functions, measuring with the appropriate metric the effect of a unit of a given species emitted locally on the climate warming, may be an efficient approach for flight routing optimisation.
- Better **correlation between contrail/contrail cirrus properties and particle emissions** is required both for prediction accuracy and for mitigation strategy.

On CO2 mitigation

- The recent progress towards ACARE 2020 CO2 goal is mainly in terms of technology maturity. The assessment exercise remains complicated and it appears necessary to discriminate the various aircraft categories.
 - Highest mitigation potential demonstrated at TRL5-6 is obtained for a Short and Medium Range aircraft equipped with a CROR, assuming Natural Laminar Flow wings and optimized trajectory.
 - Final assessment of the project (end 2017) concludes that, despite some progress, ACARE 2020 CO2 goal will not be met
- **For longer term applications, it is clear that disruptive solutions are necessary to achieve H2020 CO2 goal (-50% kg/passenger km) and to progress further towards H2050 CO2 goal (-75% kg/passenger km).**

On NOx and ultra-fine particles mitigation

- With the final status described in (§3.2), based partly on LEMCOTEC and Clean Sky inputs, consolidation has been done and satisfactory NOx reductions at airport level (air quality concern based on LTO cycle) and at cruise level (climate change concern) are achievable in 2020 at TRL5-6.
- It is recognized that lean combustion is the most appropriate way to reduce both NOx and particles. However the precise combustion technology strategy may depend on the different kinds of applications. In particular, advanced rich burn combustion may be still required for some advanced small (thrust) engines or for legacy products improvements.

Lastly, a new assessment (following previous ones done in OPTI and AGAPE European projects respectively in 2012 and 2010) has been proposed end of 2017, by FORUM-AE on the progress towards ACARE 2020 CO2 & NOx goals. It is synthesized in the following table.

	Reference 2000	ACARE 2020 Goals (at TRL6)		ACARE 2050 Goals (at TRL6)		FORUM-AE Assessment (2017) (extrapolated at TRL 5-6 in 2020)
		High Level	detailed (SRA)	High Level	detailed (SRIA)	
CO2	<i>Representative technology of aircraft & engine with 2000 EIS, & representative 2000 ATM</i>	"-50% per pass km"	aircraft: -20% to -25% engine: -15% to -20% ATM: -5% to -10%	"-75% per pass km"	aircraft & engine: -68% ATM: -12% Other: -12%	aircraft + engine +ATM: ≈ -27% Regional ≈ [-38%, -41%] SMR ≈ [-19%, -26%] LR in average per pass km
NOx (LTO)		"-80%"	engine: -60% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	"-90%"	engine: -75% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	engine: [-60%, -70%] CAEP6
NOx (Cruise)		"-80%"	Achieved through -50% Fuel Burn & -60% cruise EINOx reduction	"-90%"	Achieved through -75% Fuel Burn & further cruise EINOx reduction	~ -40% (with high uncertainty) in average per pass km
Other emissions		"damaging emissions reduced"	emissions qualitatively reduced (particles, CO, UHC) and better understanding of impacts	"emissions-free taxiing" + qualitative reduction	knowledge of emissions (particles, VOC) and better understanding of impacts	experience gained in nvPM measurement campaigns on Engines & better knowledge of engines particles emissions

FORUM-AE Final Assessment on the progress towards ACARE Goals – Vision 2017 verified in 2020

Since then, monitored RTD projects have been pursued or initiated but there is a consensus inside FORUM-AE consortium, as expressed at AEC2020 conference [32], that FORUM-AE 2017 assessment concerning the level of achievement of ACARE goals, and recommendations in terms of RTD priorities, remain mostly relevant and valid, still in 2020. One observes also, that some recommendations (for instance, the need to work on climate metrics) were duly considered.

1 Introduction

The European project FORUM-AE [FORUM on Aviation and Emissions (& Environment)] was a technical and scientific forum addressing all the issues associated to the aviation environmental concerns linked to aircraft emissions: impacts, technical solutions and regulation. It aimed at supporting the appropriate European research and innovation by giving it the necessary awareness and visibility, and was also providing a technical support to the working group on Environment and Energy of the Advisory Council for Aeronautic Research in Europe (ACARE).

In that prospect, series of focused workshops (see table below) were organized all along the project addressing: i) the scientific understanding of environmental impacts, ii) the identification of potentially promising technical and technological solutions, with an assessment of their expected benefits and maturity, iii) relevant regulation technical issues. Detailed results of all these workshops may be found in their respective proceedings available on the project’s website: www.forum-ae.eu

Workshops	Date	Location	Hosting partner
Kick-off Workshop	Sept, 19th&20th 2013	Brussels, Belgium	EC
Air Quality Workshop	January, 9th 2014	Manchester, United Kingdom	MMU
non volatile Particulate Matter (nvPM)	January, 10th 2014	Manchester, United Kingdom	MMU
Climate Change	April, 2nd & 3rd 2014	Oberpfaffenhofen, Germany	DLR
CO2 and Fuel Burn Technology	July, 1st 2014	Paris, France	Snecma
non-CO2 Technology Workshop	July, 2nd 2014	Paris, France	Snecma
Alternative Fuels Workshop (SAFF)	October, 21st 2014	Madrid, Spain	SENASA
Basket of Measures / MBM	May, 19th 2015	Toulouse, France	Airbus
Basket of Measures / CO2 standard	May, 20th 2015	Toulouse, France	Airbus
Mid-Term Meeting	July, 8th & 9th 2015	Brussels, Belgium	EC
Inventory Workshop	Sept., 1st & 2nd 2015	Zurich, Switzerland	Zurich Airport
ATM	19& 20/01/2016	Brussels, Belgium	Eurocontrol
Air Quality Workshop (n°2)	April, 14th 2016	Amsterdam, Netherlands	NLR
non volatile Particulate Matter (nvPM) (n°2)	April, 15th 2016	Amsterdam, Netherlands	NLR
Climate Change (n°2) (with ECATS 2nd Conf)	November, 8th 2016	Athens, Grece	ECATS
non-CO2 Technology Workshop (n°2)	March, 8th & 9th 2017	Berlin, Deutschland	Rolls-Royce Deutschland
CO2 and Fuel Burn Technology (n°2) + elect. a/c	May, 10th & 11th 2017	Reims, France	Onera
Final Conference	15th June 2017	Paris, France	Safran AE

FORUM-AE technical workshops [2013-2017]

FORUM-AE monitored also the European research and innovation in the field of aviation environmental issues linked to emissions by compiling relevant information from all existing EU projects and main national ones, and assessed the progress towards the ACARE environmental goals (see appendix 3).

FORUM-AE consortium involved a very large range of expertise on the numerous subjects, with a good balance between industrial and academic partners. The quality of this consortium contributed clearly to the successful exchanges. The final conference, which took place in June 2017 was an opportunity for preliminary dissemination of the project’s results and conclusions.

FORUM-AE consortium

The present synthesis is based on the output of all the workshops and of the monitoring work, and contains the final assessment against ACARE pollutant emissions goals (following the mid-term assessment in 2015, and older ones by OPTI and AGAPE European projects respectively in 2012 and 2010).

It is mainly based on the contractual deliverable “D4.22” issued in December 2017 but circulated only inside the consortium and to the European Commission. This publishable synthesis aims at a better dissemination of the project outputs; Moreover, as the landscape has evolved since then, a high level up-dated status is provided in Chapter 6 and footnotes were added to inform on new available relevant information.

Nota: General information on the project, its principles and organisation are recalled in appendix 1. This appendix is completed with the organisation scheme of a new European network, which was envisaged by the consortium to pursue this technical work addressing aviation environmental issues, with an enlarged scope including noise and complementary focus on new energy carriers.

2 Environmental Impact from Aviation

2.1 Main results and conclusions on Inventories

2.1.1 General status

Aircrafts emissions inventories establish a link between an anthropogenic activity and an associated impact such as air quality or climate change. They serve as input to models for studying changes in atmospheric composition and properties up to impacts. In time-series mode, they also provide information on progress and developments in aviation emission technology. Particular care is however needed when preparing emission inventories, as their values and uncertainties directly enter into an assessment or impact analysis.

The inventory focus for environmental impacts is mainly on CO₂, NO_x, particles emitted during the flight cruise when addressing climate, and on NO_x, particles, CO and UHC emitted during the flight LTO cycle when addressing air quality. A large variety of methods and tools are used today for inventory, and it is difficult to recommend specific ones. The table below lists some of the major European ones at airport level. More than focusing on individual tools, better is to have recommended practices and bench work studies. CAEPort virtual airport may be for instance a good choice for comparing different LTO inventories approaches.

Open ALAQS	Application, available through EUROCONTROL	www.eurocontrol.int
LASPORT 2.2	Application, publicly available	www.janicke.de
ADMS	Application, publicly available	www.cerc.co.uk
POLEMICA	No publicly available	See [17]
AEDT and EDMS 5.1	Application, publicly available	www.faa.gov

Table 1: Some of European airport emissions inventory and air quality models (more details also available on www.forum-ae.eu) + FAA model

Global fleet inventory was for instance performed in the frame of the Clean Sky [24] Technology Evaluator in order to assess the benefit of introducing more fuel burn efficient technology, and also in the REACT4C European project in order to be used as an input for climate impact assessment.

Figure 1: Clean Sky Technology Evaluator output - CO₂ of 2020 fleet including 100% of Clean Sky technology introduction

FORUM-AE status, permitted to put emphasis on the following aspects:

When considering inventories at airports, performance based calculation (with actual time in mode and thrust settings) reveals some discrepancy with the generic LTO cycle based calculation (as described in ICAO Doc9889¹), which is illustrated below.

Figure 2: Comparison of LTO emissions calculated for Zurich Airport (2008 data) based on performance-based LTO modelling versus ICAO-standard LTO modelling [Source: Zurich Airport]²

Also, field emissions measurements (close to the plume of aircraft at idle during taxiing, or even at take-off thrust setting), show possible differences in terms of emission indices compared to certified values as reported in the ICAO emissions database (ICAO edb³).

Fig. 3: Comparison of aircraft engine NOx emission indices at ground-idle (taxi) conditions obtained from direct pollutant emissions measurements versus certified values [Source: BUW and NAU]

¹ CAEP 10 SG 2015 approved public version: <https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Documents/Doc%209889.SGAR.WG2.Initial%20Update.pdf#search=Doc%209889>

² An emission excel calculator is publicly available on <https://www.zurich-airport.com/the-company/noise-policy-and-the-environment/air-quality/>

³ www.easa.europa.eu/domains/environment/icao-aircraft-engine-emissions-databank

2.1.2 Recommendations and needs

The following key statements and recommendations were done by FORUM-AE in 2017.

- 1) The first major topic requiring further effort concerns particulate matter (PM) emissions, in particular non-volatile PM (nvPM) emissions, in the landing and take-off (LTO) phases as well as in cruise (or non-LTO) phase. Collections of mass and number data of nvPM emissions (in emission index format, EI) are still limited but work has been efficiently initiated in the framework of ICAO-CAEP⁴. Linked to cruise nvPM, further work is needed on the correlation between ground nvPM EIs and those in cruise. Preliminary nvPM cruise emission indices (mass and number EIs) are available for use in aviation nvPM inventory-making, however to be “handled with (utmost) care”⁵. In parallel there is a need to consolidate volatile particles inventories (in particular linked to PM_{2.5} inventories).
- 2) The following set of RTD topics are linked to general enhancements in methodologies and modelling of aircraft engine and APU emissions in order to end up with accurate-as-possible emission inventories and projections:
 - First of all, opportunities should be taken to carry out model inter-comparison or cross-validation in order to raise the average level of aviation emission modelling globally
 - Also improve the vertical integration from LTO to cruise calculations, so-called “gate-to-gate” emission modelling, by removing any existing transition in approach or change in modelling between, for instance, below and above the LTO-related altitude of 3000ft
 - Give momentum to the further introduction of performance-based LTO modelling, versus the ICAO-standard LTO modelling, in order to model aircraft LTO and thus airport emissions more realistically
 - Encourage measurement and further use of actually measured times in mode, thrust settings and emission factors of aircraft engines in operation, again, in order to model aircraft and airport emissions more realistically. Not only should we continue and rely on certified LTO emission indices (available in the ICAO emissions databank) but also derive emission indices from concentration measurements of aircraft plumes at airports, and to cross-validate and assess critically the ICAO certified values (and raise any issue if the certified values appear not fully satisfactory). Using both in parallel is most likely the preferred option with reliable ICAO values on the one hand, and timely and local conditional values on the other hand (e.g., in taxi /idle operation phase, actual conditions will certainly differ from the LTO standard 7% thrust setting and 26 minutes time in mode)
 - Aircraft auxiliary power units (APUs) are a relevant emission source at airports, and therefore it is of importance to consolidate substantially the currently inconstant set of APU emission factors⁶.

⁴ Since 2017, all engine manufacturers have performed nvPM certification campaigns on all their in-production engine models, in order to be able to pursue their production after 1st January 2020. It is expected that all this data will become public before end of 2020 - beginning of 2021, in the ICAO emissions data base, as it is the case for NO_x,

⁵ Some work has been performed since 2017 to progress on this topic, in particular in a European project (No. MOVE/C2/SER/2014-269/SI2.706115) motivated by EASA. See [28]. The topic is still addressed in 2020 in ICAO/CAEP technical group.

⁶ Various campaigns were performed since FORUM-AE end, in particular by MMU in Jetscreen and by Safran Power Unit

- 3) Furthermore, methods and tools to calculate aviation emissions for emission inventory and projection purposes should be sensitive to new technology and operational improvements (including mitigation measures) or otherwise be adapted or newly developed/introduced. Also in this respect, the fuel flow methods developed by Boeing (version 2) and DLR are considered estimating the cruise NO_x emission indices (EI NO_x) reasonably well when applied to conventional engine combustion technology (although comparison of the two methods might perhaps be done more accurately for a number of representative flights/missions). For more advanced (low NO_x) combustion technology however, further development, testing and validation of the (adjusted) fuel flow methods is needed prior to wider application for global aviation NO_x emission modelling and inventory-making.
- 4) Finally, related to short and longer term projections of aviation (and emissions), modelling advancement and improvements are required in dealing with (airport and airspace) capacity constraints.

2.2 Main results and conclusions on Air Quality

2.2.1 General Status

Legislation, Regulation and Directives

Despite some regional disparities, all elements of the air quality causality chain are regulated either by emission sources regulations, work place concentration regulations, and national ambient air quality standards (NAAQS); aviation is not exempted. The only gaps found are in the domain of small aircraft engines and auxiliary power units (APU).

In the case of France, as an example, the 12 largest airports fall within the jurisdiction of the independent administrative authority ACNUSA; this covers research, measurement, monitoring, regulation and planning issues linked to aviation noise, emissions and its impacts. Established in 2013, a working group on Air Quality and Airports aims to objectify the impact of airport-related activities on the quality of local and regional air. A set of indicators (emissions, impacts, measures) were therefore defined as well as recommendations for monitoring air quality and inventorying pollutant emissions, for example, aircraft taxi-out with n-1 engine and APU limitation of running times; improving ground access traffic and promoting public transport; and encouraging development of “greener” ground support equipment (GSE).

Measurements

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission (EC) together with the network of national Air Quality Reference Laboratories (AQUILA) organised a particulate matter (PM) quality assurance & control campaign in 2015 in order to further harmonise PM measurement methods. The following conclusions were drawn from this campaign:

- EU reference method shows good reproducibility
- There is an excellent performance and comparability of National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) and method
- Data Quality Objectives (DQO, in 2008/50/EC Directive) of $\pm 25\%$ are mostly met for PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀.

In 2015, a measurement campaign on ultrafine particles (UFP) took place around Amsterdam Schiphol airport. Results of measurements indicate a clear influence of aviation emissions in the airport vicinity with elevated number concentrations of UFP. Particle numbers decrease with increasing distance from source; during one sample day, numbers decreased from 200,000 particles per cm³ next to a runway to 20,000 approximately 5 km away. As observed at Schiphol airport, aircraft emissions are distinguished from other sources by the very small particle size, predominantly between 10 and 20 nm. Further work is however required on the constituents of these particles and whether similar observations are seen at other airports.

Air quality impact modelling and assessments

Earlier U.S. studies (covering all human activities) show that health impacts from fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) are dominating compared to other pollutants (ozone [O₃] and air toxics). Future year aviation-related health impacts in U.S. might increase by a factor of approx. 6 from 2005 to 2025.

Incorporating for change in climate might add another approx. 7% (“climate penalty”) shown in recent studies.

Changes in background emissions (of ammonia [NH₃]) will play a key role in aviation-attributable inorganic PM_{2.5} in future. New knowledge on secondary organic aerosol (SOA) shifts both magnitude and composition of aviation-attributable PM_{2.5}. Stringent revisions to health-based standards will likely exacerbate aviation-related contributions to exceedances in non-attainment areas in the U.S. Nevertheless, the relative contribution of aviation to local PM_{2.5} concentrations remains small in comparison to other source contributions and very small compared to the air quality limit (of 25µg/m³, annual average).

Ultrafine particles (UFPs) are potentially a bigger issue; Simple and early stage observations in the vicinity of Los Angeles International Airport (LAX) showed that particle number concentrations were 2 times higher than background concentrations at distances of up to 10 miles (16 km) from the airport (see Figure below).

Figure 3: Particle number concentration against background concentration in the vicinity of Los Angeles International Airport (Source: Hudda et al. 2014; Ref. [15a])

Additional UFP studies and evaluations involving a representative number of airports are needed though, as well as more fundamental research work to:

- Reduce uncertainties in aircraft non-volatile PM (nvPM) emissions and precursors of volatile PM (vPM)
- Characterise ultrafine particle (UFP) impacts (mass versus number on a size-resolved basis)
- Enhance local-scale dispersion models to represent aircraft sources adequately for accurate local-scale impact assessment.

The Netherlands STACKS+ dispersion model in close combination with the NLR LEAS-iT emission model were used to estimate concentration levels of ultrafine particles (UFP) in the vicinity of Amsterdam Schiphol airport. Modelling results were compared to results from relevant measurements by ECN in 2015. A scaling factor has been derived to correlate modelled PM₁₀ mass concentration into UFP number concentrations; i.e., 1 µg PM₁₀ per m³ equals 400,000 ultrafine particles per cm³ (1-hourly mean). Using this correlation in long-term model calculations of UFP/PM₁₀ concentrations, annual-averaged results show Schiphol airport contributions of 3000

ultrafine particles per cm^3 are possible at 10 kilometer distances. In residential areas closest to Schiphol airport, annual mean contributions might increase up to 10,000 ultrafine particles per cm^3 ; in 5% of the time, this contribution can amount to 50,000 per cm^3 . NB: Compared to approx. 15,000 ultrafine particles per cm^3 for road traffic in inner-city streets.

“CAEP Model Airport” based evaluations (or the like) are relevant model-comparison exercises; differences in modelling results do of course appear, which is however acceptable if at least their background is discussed and clarified. At ICAO-CAEP level, ADMS-Airport (CERC, UK), ALAQS-AV (EUROCONTROL), EDMS (US FAA), LASPORT (Janicke, DE), PEGAS (RU) and last but not least PolEmiCa (NAU, Ukraine) were submitted to this CAEPport test; Open-ALAQS (EUROCONTROL; under development in the framework of SESAR; see www.sesarju.eu) was submitted later to this test, and is now available too.

An important driver of model developments is the need to quantify operational improvements in aviation emission inventories and projections. This can be for the purpose of cost-benefit-analysis and/or for communication purposes and/or for optimisation of operational practices. It is encouraged to further work on the known gaps in airport emissions modelling as highlighted in table 2, which is an update of the table shown at the 2014 FORUM-AE Air Quality workshop (Ref. [1]).

Modelling of airport emissions confirms the relative importance of aircraft emissions compared to other airport emission sources (in particular for nitrogen oxides [NO_x]; however, to be checked for PM). Enhanced modelling of this particular emission source might include:

- Complex LTO-cycle: stop&go, variable queuing, flex take-off, variable departure or arrival (no fixed SID/STAR)
- Fuel: alternative fuels, blends, in addition to standard Jet-A1
- Operational Improvement (OI): now relevant in the context of SESAR
- Auxiliary power unit (APU): more complex with emerging aircraft ground energy systems (AGES)
- Emerging topics: particulate matter (PM; mass and number) and carbon dioxide (CO₂; in the scope of climate impact).

Of particular interest in the field of air quality impacts of aviation at multiple scales are the following developments:

- Aircraft plume dynamics modelling: 3D integral plume modelling accounting for, amongst others, crosswind effects, ambient turbulence and plume downwash in aircraft trailing vortices
- Dispersion modelling at local airport scale: analytical solution for dispersion from area sources (such as Rapid Dispersion Code, RDC) reduces computation time with more than 99%, enabling multi-airport analysis within reasonable times at the loss of 5-10% in certainty for long-term averages
- Local and regional hybrid approach: combination of the finer outcome of rapid dispersion model prediction (airport only; <100 m grid cell) and the coarser outcome of chemistry transport modelling (CTM) pollutant prediction (all sources; e.g., 36 km grid cell).

Air quality from aircraft cruise emissions

In addition to the local and regional effects of landing and take-off (LTO) emissions, aircraft cruise emissions may contribute indirectly to trans-boundary air pollution. Combining model calculations of long range transport and secondary particle formation from cruise related precursors (Sulphur dioxides [SO_x], and ozone [O₃] via nitrogen oxides [NO_x]) and non-aviation background concentrations of ammonia (NH₃) and sulphur dioxides (SO₂) with high population density in South-East Asia, results in additional global aviation effects.

In terms of risk of premature mortality associated with poor surface air quality (mainly due to PM_{2.5}), approx. 1% of global outdoor air quality health impacts might be due to aviation emissions compared to all sectors today (if the indirect effects are completely attributed to aviation). In this, according to MIT study (shared within FORUM-AE; see [1]), LTO accounts for 25% and cruise 75% globally (regional differences exist: LTO accounts for 43% in US, 49% in Europe, 9% in Asia). Bearing in mind the lack of knowledge on high altitude to surface transport of emissions, we currently might stick to the accepted belief of a maximum of 1% aviation contribution overall.

Secondary aerosols from NO_x as well as SO_x emitted by aircraft engines in cruise seem to contribute relatively most to the PM_{2.5} mass concentrations on the ground; whereas the black carbon (BC) or nvPM contribution seems to be minor (more negligible). Moreover, PM_{2.5} mass concentrations (linked to aircraft cruise emissions) estimated by MIT remains quite small; however, further uncertainty assessment would be key information.

2.2.2 Recommendations and needs

The following key statements and recommendations were done by FORUM-AE in 2017.

- 1) The key airport and aircraft pollutants, linked to air quality (AQ) impact and environmental concern, are nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and particles. The particle issue should be addressed both in terms of PM_{2.5} mass concentration and in terms of ultrafine particles (UFP) for which number concentration appears more relevant. Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) emissions from the aircraft engine might be an important contributor to PM_{2.5}.
- 2) There is a strong regulation framework on emission source level, at work place level and at ambient air quality level. However, nothing exists (yet) for auxiliary power units (APUs) which explains strong uncertainties on their emission factors (in particular for NO_x and particles).
- 3) The measurements in Europe of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in the airport vicinity are rather well harmonised and demonstrate a good quality level; this does not really apply to ultrafine particles. A robust assessment would be useful and is recommended⁷.
- 4) PM_{2.5} mass concentrations linked to airport activities appear most of the time to be small compared to contributions from other sources, and very small against air quality limits. UFP contributions from airport activities are of stronger concern with elevated concentrations

⁷ Nevertheless, some robust UFP measurements have been performed more recently in Europe (see the ACI EUROPE UFP Report 2018: <https://www.aci-europe.org/downloads/resources/Ultra-Fine%20Particles%20at%20Airports.pdf>), but sufficient harmonisation-standardisation should be checked

observed not only close to runways but also distances away from the airport. However, this should be consolidated with more airport studies.

- 5) Airport emission inventory and air quality modelling improvements are required⁸, which will make models more accurately predict concentrations at and around airport.

General recommendations and status:

- Further consolidation is needed in knowledge of relevant airport emissions sources and their activity (performance), emission factor and calculation algorithm.
- Better representativeness of operational data should be pursued
- In that prospect, there is a need for harmonisation in performance based emissions modelling
- CAEPport offers a good benchmarking case to compare codes
- Modelling should be validated against field measurements.
- Status is summarised in the table below:

Source	Activity	Emission factor	Calculation
Aircraft engine	Stop&go behaviour, Idle vs taxi, flex take-off	ICAO Emissions Data Bank (EDB); PM is work in progress	Fuel Flow Method (e.g. Boeing 2 FFM); First Order Approx. (FOA3) for nvPM & PM2.5
APU	Duration for Environmental Control System (ECS)	Very coarse in Doc 9889	Simple product
Aircraft frame	Brakes, tires	Assumptions	Simple product
GSE	Inventory good, else poor	EU Non-Road Mobile Machinery (EUNRMM) emissions & standards	Simple product
Stationary Sources	Usually well known	EMEP-EEA guidance, manufacturer data	Simple product
Landside vehicles	Fair, lots of assumptions	Handbook Emission Factors for Road Transport (HBEFA), EEA COPERT, etc.	Simple product

Table 2: Status & Identified Gaps in Airports Inventory

Red: improvements still required; Yellow: in-progress or less required; Green: knowledge is good
Emission [in grams] = Emission Factor [in g/s or g/km] x Activity [in s or km distance covered]

Recommendations more specific to particles (concentration predictions require important modelling improvements):

- Better non-volatile PM emission factors and better knowledge on volatile PM precursors are needed. In this respect, and as long as nvPM data availability is insufficient for main aircraft engines, potential improvement of the first order approximation (FOA3) method could be encouraged⁹

⁸ A part of the suggested improvement effort is currently carried out in the H2020 project AVIATOR (Assessing aViation emission Impact on local Air quality at airports: TOWards Regulation): <https://aviatorproject.eu/>

⁹ Since then, the FOA3 approximation to estimate nvPM described has been improved and is called SCOPE11 approximation (see [31]). Doc9889 has also been up-dated with the SCOPE11 model.

- UFP dispersion prediction should be consolidated by replacing coarse hypotheses such as a correlation between UFP (number concentration) and PM10 (mass concentration).
- 6) Aircraft cruise emissions might impact ground air quality. Most modelling effort on this topic is currently performed in the U.S.A. It appears that NO_x and SO_x emitted in cruise by the aircraft engines have a dominant contribution to ground PM_{2.5} whereas nvPM cruise emissions are more marginal. However, estimation of uncertainties associated to the predicted levels is strongly needed¹⁰.

¹⁰ Since beginning of 2019, work is on-going at CAEP level to precisely deliver more robust cruise correlations

2.3 Main results and conclusions on Climate Change

2.3.1 General Status

- Commonly non-CO₂ climate impacts of aviation are said to be potentially of the same order of magnitude as CO₂ climate impacts. Taking a closer look at **absolute values** in terms of radiative forcing (RF), estimates still show a broad range, which corresponds to mid to low *level of scientific understanding (LOSU)* as described by IPCC (Lee et al., 2009) and since then has not been reduced substantially.
- However, for developing mitigation options, it is crucial to provide robust **relative estimates**, when comparing a mitigation solution with the reference case. This means that mitigation solutions have to demonstrate that overall they reduce climate impact under such uncertainty conditions.
- Amongst non-CO₂ impacts, in particular of NO_x emissions and of contrail/contrail cirrus, recent studies, which further investigated the issue testing for robust relative estimates, were presented during the FORUM-AE workshops. Some results from a set of modelling studies were shown, where trade-off effects of alternative routing mitigation scenarios were investigated. Main purpose is to emphasize sensitivities of non-CO₂ impacts and to give indications for robust behaviour.

Figure 4: Aviation-induced RF from different components ; updated figure from IPCC taken from Grewe et al., 2017 (ref [13]) (bars and uncertainty ranges)

- A multi-model study performed within the European project REACT4C quantifies aviation **NO_x impact** on O₃ and the impact of simplified **mitigation scenarios** of flying lower and higher by 2000 ft (Sovde et al. 2014 ; see Forum-ae Climate Change Workshop proceedings in ref [1]),.

Specifically, an mean absolute estimate of radiative forcing associated with NO_x emissions from aviation of 5.2 (0.8-8.0) mW/m² is calculated by a set of five chemistry transport models, taking into account short-term ozone formation, long-term cooling due to reduced methane concentrations, and induced long-term ozone perturbation associated with methane change.

Figure 5: Aviation NO_x 2006 (left) and Ozone perturbation (right)

- In order to investigate operational mitigation strategies by alternative routing, two options for simplified mitigation strategies of “flying lower” and “flying higher” by 2000 ft were similarly evaluated as relative values in REACT4C. Changes in atmospheric concentrations of ozone O₃ (see Figure) and methane, lead to a corresponding reduction in radiative forcing of -1.7(-2.6 to -0.8) mW/m² and increase of 1.8(0.7 to 3.0) mW/m², respectively.

Figure 6: Mitigation scenarios - effect on O₃ of flight lower (left) or higher (right) compared to the base

RF/mW/m ²	Mean	Range
Aviation	5.2	[0.8;8.0]
Flying lower	-1.7	[-2.6;-0.8]
Flying higher	1.8	[0.7;3.0]

Figure 7: Mitigation scenarios: climate impact of NO_x emissions when flying lower or higher

- Providing absolute and relative estimates for other non-CO₂ impacts, i.e. contrail and contrail-cirrus, soot, sulphate and water vapour, as done in REACT4C (FP7) for the simplified mitigation studies indicate a similar behaviour when considering a set of non-CO₂ impacts (Lim et al.,

Matthes et al., in [12]). Recent results from these sensitivity studies indicate that “flying higher” reduces CO₂ impact, but increases a set of non-CO₂ impacts, while “flying lower” increases CO₂ but reduces a set of non-CO₂ impacts. As such results are based on a small number of model simulations, the values provided can only be seen as an indication on sensitivity, and do not represent a comprehensive assessment. No uncertainty range is indicated here. However, comparing individual estimates (indicated by symbols) demonstrates **robust** behaviour of investigated non-CO₂ effects.

Figure 8: REACT4C study: CO₂/non-CO₂ trade-off when flying higher (left) or lower (right). Ranges indicating no uncertainty level but only range of results from individual model calculations.

- Operational measures may be highly relevant to mitigate climate impact as non- CO₂ climate effects **vary with space and time**, as illustrated for NO_x emissions and contrails. Adequate means for describing spatial and temporal dependence are climate-cost functions. A one-day case study shows that climate optimal routing can achieve large reductions (up to 60%) for westbound flights from Europe to USA (Frömming et al., Grewe et al., Matthes et al. in in ref [12]).

Figure 9: Meteorological spatial variation: geopotential heights (left) & wind velocity (right)

Figure 10: Spatial distributions: Contrail cirrus (left) and total NO_x (right)

- Concerning contrails & contrail cirrus, IPCC2013¹¹ states: “... for year 2011, the combined contrail and contrail-cirrus ERF from aviation is assessed to be 0.05 [0.02 to 0.15] Wm⁻² (low confidence).”
- An urgent need to rise confidence levels or to reduce uncertainties regarding the contrail (and contrail cirrus) induced climate impact is often stated. Therefore it is needed to spot the sources of the uncertainties. Contrail formation itself is a process that is completely under thermodynamic control, and the formation criterion (the so-called Schmidt-Appleman criterion recalled by K. Gierens¹²) is a consequence of fundamental conservation laws from physics: mass, momentum, and energy conservation. Whether a contrail is persistent or not is clearly determined by the ambient relative humidity (ice super-saturation or not). So far, there are no uncertainties at all.
- Uncertainties arise from modelling imperfections (for instance prediction of super-saturation in a weather model, representation of contrail and cirrus microphysics in large-scale models), from uncertain initial conditions (e.g. soot emission index, fuel flow rate, actual aircraft weight, actual meteorological conditions, etc.¹³). These uncertainties can principally be reduced in a case-by-case mode. But they cannot be reduced to zero, because a model is still a model, i.e. a reduced image of nature. The price one has to pay for the reduction of natural complexity is uncertainties.
- The largest source of uncertainty is, however, the sheer natural variability which is evident to everybody who keeps an eye on the contrail-covered sky. These variable conditions allow contrails that have optical thicknesses ranging from invisible to very bright, lifetimes ranging from a few minutes or even less to many hours, widths ranging from about 100 m (similar to the wingspan) to many kilometres, and individual radiative forcings ranging from a strong cooling effect (mainly in the twilight hours and over a dark background, e.g. ocean water) to a strong warming effect (in particular at night and over otherwise cirrus free background). These variable conditions are of natural origin, and the resulting uncertainty cannot be reduced. This is rather a statistical problem.

Figure 11: Contrails & contrail cirrus: formation, persistency, radiative forcing... that's the questions
(Photographs courtesy of Kostas Eleftheratos)

- In the light of this conclusion the question arises, how the climate impact of contrails can best be mitigated knowing that contrails can have very different individual climate forcings, from a large warming to a large cooling effect.

¹¹ <https://www.ipcc.ch/reports/> ; see AR5 Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis

¹² See FORUM-AE Climate Change 2014 workshop proceedings in [1] ; Schmidt-Appleman OD criteria was also recently assessed with 3D simulations by Onera (see [19])

¹³ Nucleation role of vPM including sulphur based vPM, should perhaps require also some investigation

- One possibility to study contrail cirrus is to analyse processes in a climate model using a 2-moment scheme. Estimates of contrail coverage with such a more detailed representation lead to values higher than earlier estimates. From the studies it is also shown that the vertical distribution of aviation is of large importance, i.e. when using AEDT¹⁴ versus AERO2K¹⁵ inventories estimates are significantly higher.
- Reducing soot emissions is expected to reduce initial ice crystal number. This reduction may be achieved by combustor technology improvements (e.g. better optimisation, lean combustion strategy) or by cleaner fuels (less aromatics or less sulfur). Consequently biofuels most often with zero aromatics will be beneficial. Clarification on the respective effect of non-volatile particles (nvPM) and other particles (volatile particles including sulphate based particles) should be pursued¹⁶. Reducing soot emission by 80% results in a mitigation of contrail cirrus radiative forcing by 50%, showing a non-linear behaviour.
- The first nvPM particles international standard agreed in 2016 will make available reliable measurements data on the ground. However, estimates of cruise nvPM are needed by atmospheric modeller in order to provide an assessment of climate impact. A need is expressed for a better link between engines and what atmospheric modellers use in the 3D (CFD) calculations.
- Long-term prospects for substantially reducing specific emission of emitted species, e.g. NO_x and contrail generated, are good. However, the question remains to what extent increase of air traffic volume can be compensated by efficiency and mitigation processes.
- Another point which raised from FORUM-AE workshop discussion and which was stressed at the ICAO/CAEP/ISG (Impact Science Group) workshop¹⁷, is the sensitivity to the metric choice, which is fundamental when comparing CO₂/non-CO₂ effects. Most often, radiative forcing has been used up to now but RF may not be relevant to measure long term effects. Appropriate metric remains therefore an open issue, in particular for operational mitigation. An overview on other climate metrics currently used can be found in [14]. By way of example, one metric which reduces the dependency on the time horizon selected is the average temperature response (ATR), which is the mean future temperature development over a period up to the chosen time horizon, e.g. typically 20 or 50 years. Such an average temperature response can be calculated for a pulse emission (similar to a single decision) or for sustained emissions or an emission scenario (similar to a strategic decision for e.g. ways to operate or technology options).

¹⁴ Aviation Environmental Design Tool (AEDT) ; see <http://aedt.faa.gov/>

¹⁵ European project Aero2K - Global aviation inventories for 2002 and 2026 ; Eyers et al 2004 ; QinetiQ/04/01113

¹⁶ Recent paper [38] may be a relevant reference

¹⁷ Washington, February 2015

- Promising mitigation concepts are expected to represent a combination of technologies and operational improvements, where the different aspects of airframe, engine and operations are considered at the same time. Fuel efficiency has improved over the years being equivalent to a CO₂ reduction. At the same time, technology targeted also non-CO₂ emission reductions. Results are promising, however making clear that more work is needed, and here most efficient will be joint research between industry and academia, but also between disciplines.

Research on mitigation concepts for climate impact of aviation regularly brings different disciplines together, which is a particular characteristic of ECATS International Association (AISBL), working interdisciplinary, e.g. engineers work together with researchers and experts from atmospheric science.

2.3.2 Recommendations and needs

The following key statements and recommendations were done by FORUM-AE in 2017.

- 1) Studies show how results (estimates) vary with and depend on different emission inventories and so **sensitivity analysis to emissions inventories** are recommended.
- 2) Clear **documentation of assumptions in future scenarios** and sensitivity studies on such assumptions are also fully relevant for gaining understanding of the impact of the assumptions.
- 3) Metric is still an open key issue. Quantitative estimates should be provided for a set of typical metrics (e.g. radiative forcing, average temperature response, and global warming potential...) to **demonstrate sensitivity of results** on choice of metric, by using several different metrics in an overall assessment. For a single metric selected, there is a specific need of **careful selection of calculation methods and metric elements**, appropriate to the question to be answered.
- 4) In terms of defining **new climate metrics**, relating to the strategic climate policy 2°C goal as spelled out by Paris Agreement¹⁸ at COP21 in 2015, an associated metric is required, for providing guidance in the way to achieve it. Additionally, a need becomes apparent for a metric which reflects the long-term climate impact.
- 5) **Sources of uncertainties** must still be analysed; and there is a need to develop means for robust decisions under uncertainty.
- 6) When targeting to assess overall climate impact, an assessment must comprise set of aviation effects, as new technology might influence environmental impacts for several components, e.g. more fuel efficiency to produce more contrails. It is required to combine benefits from a technology with **possible trade-off impacts** from non-CO₂ impacts.
- 7) Specifically for contrail formation and associated climate impact future research needs to sort out aircraft technology improvements and evolution and resulting impacts on contrail formation.

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/international/negotiations/paris_en

Here also the need has become apparent that a better link and understanding between **particle emissions and contrail cirrus formation** and optical properties is required.

- 8) For providing quantitative estimates of e.g. mitigation potential of aviation, **scenarios for future air traffic** are needed. Hence, particular care and attention is needed, when defining future scenarios. An assessment of mitigation options towards challenging climate targets is required, in order to analyse future mitigation potentials and sustainable pathways. Here it will be critical to identify entry into service and market penetration of new, promising mitigation technologies and concepts. It is of interest to analyse climate impact assessment under forward projections of technology, in order to identify to what extent climate targets are achievable.
- 9) Technology programmes which aim to design future technologies are required to perform an **overall climate impact assessment** comprising to deliver climate impact assessment and climate impact mitigation potential for promising technology options, as currently envisaged within technology programmes, e.g. European Research Programme Clean Sky 2 (Joint Technology Initiative).
- 10) **Climate-optimised flight routing** must be further developed, ideally considering the **individual weather situation**. Using climate change functions, measuring with the appropriate metric the effect of an unit of a given species emitted locally on the climate warming, may be an efficient approach for flight routing optimisation.
- 11) Better **correlation between contrail/contrail cirrus properties and particle emissions** is required both for prediction accuracy and for mitigation strategy.

3 Mitigation Solutions

3.1 CO₂ emissions Technological mitigation (aircraft & engines)

3.1.1 General status

The content of this synthesis is based on workshops technical contributions with induced discussions, and possible further iterations after the workshops. It includes main results, provides assessment on the progress towards ACARE CO₂ goals, and gives a list of key statements together with recommendations on relevant RTD orientations.

Context and ACARE CO₂ Goals

Because of climate change concern, CO₂ reduction is a major issue for aviation transport since beginning of the century. The general context encouraging for significant CO₂ reduction in air transport, has been reinforced in particular by the COP21 summit in 2015, the ICAO carbon neutral growth objective (ICAO 38th assembly in 2013), and the IATA objective. To contribute to global aviation CO₂ reduction, the first international CO₂ standard applying on aircrafts has been validated by ICAO in 2016, market based measures are envisaged (ICAO CORSIA recommendations, EU ETS at European level), and sustainable alternative fuels (SAF) solutions are promoted. Lastly, in order to develop concretely more efficient aircrafts in the future, the Advisory Council for Aeronautics Research in Europe (ACARE) has fixed very challenging CO₂ reductions goals (Vision 2020 and Flight Path 2050 [2]) for research and technology development European programs, applying on aircraft technology, engine technology and aircraft operations. Assessment of this RTD effort is one of the tasks of FORUM-AE project. The following table recalls the mid-term assessment performed by FORUM-AE in 2015.

	Reference 2000	ACARE 2020 Goals (at TRL6)		ACARE 2050 Goals (at TRL6)		FORUM-AE Assessment (2015) (extrapol. at TRL6 in 2020)
		High Level	detailed (SRA)	High Level	detailed (SRIA)	
CO ₂	<i>Representative technology of aircraft & engine with 2000 EIS, & representative 2000 ATM</i>	"-50% per pass km"	aircraft: -20% to -25% engine: -15% to -20% ATM: -5% to -10%	"-75% per pass km"	aircraft & engine: -68% ATM: -12% Other: -12%	aircraft + engine +ATM: ≈ -38% in average per pass km
NO _x (LTO)		"-80%"	engine: -60% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	"-90%"	engine: -75% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	engine: [-55%, -65%] CAEP6
NO _x (Cruise)		"-80%"	Achieved through -50% Fuel Burn & -60% cruise EINO _x reduction	"-90%"	Achieved through -75% Fuel Burn & further cruise EINO _x reduction	not quantified
Other emissions		"damaging emissions reduced"	emissions qualitatively reduced (particles, CO, UHC) and better understanding of impacts	"emissions-free taxiing" + qualitative reduction	knowledge of emissions (particles, VOC) and better understanding of impacts	better knowledge of engines particles emissions

Table 3: Recall of ACARE 2020 & 2050 Goals and FORUM-AE 2015 mid-term assessment

Fundamentals on aircraft & engine efficiency

For a given architecture, such as a turbofan, engine efficiency relies on thermal and propulsive efficiencies which depend on BPR/FPR and OPR design parameters together with components efficiencies. Energy budget linked to the engine will depend also on the choice between ducted or unducted engine configuration, on its integration to the aircraft, on its weight. Isochoric combustion (Humphrey) cycles instead of isobar combustion (Brayton) cycle permits also theoretically to increase the thermal efficiency.

Figure 12 : Propulsion system efficiency analysis (N. Tantot – FORUM-AE CO2 Workshop 2017)

Aircraft efficiency is well described in Breguet formula, and depends both on aircraft aerodynamics and weight.

Results from major European programs towards TRL4-5

The three key European projects E-BREAK (fully completed in 2017 ; see [21]), LEMCOTEC and ENOVAL (completed in 2018 ; see [20]&[22a&b]), have contributed to mature a large number of engine technologies up to TRL5 in order to achieve appreciable CO₂ reductions compared to year 2000 representative technologies for various aircraft categories : regional aircraft, short and medium range aircraft, large aircraft, as well as turboshaft regarding E-BREAK. E-BREAK was indeed covering a large range of enabling technologies (higher temperature or lighter materials, variable engine systems, sealings...) whereas LEMCOTEC and ENOVAL, were more focused on engine architecture and improvement of main component efficiencies (respectively for high pressure and low pressure components). LEMCOTEC supported also major activity on lean combustion technology and ENOVAL supported some work on propulsion integration, through slimmer nacelle and variable area fan nozzle. Assuming the use of the various improvements developed in the project combined with higher OPRs in comparison to reference engine, LEMCOTEC CO₂ mitigation estimations per aircraft/engine type are provided here after.

	LEMCOTEC			
Category	RTF (impeller)	RTF (all axial)	SMR (CROR)	LR (GTF)
Reference	B717-200	B717-200	A320-200	A330-200
% CO ₂ reduction	19	20	28,5	23,4
Comments	Improvements only from the engine			

Table 4: LEMCOTEC CO₂ reduction assessment results

Figure 13: ENOVAL - overview of investigated technologies

The COBRA European project, in coordination with Russian partners, was a more specific project, pursuing VITAL work on a contra-rotating turbofan and was completed in 2018. It aimed in particular at demonstrating better noise level than what was estimated in VITAL, keeping the same efficiency. The project relied on two demonstrators: one based on the Russian NK-93 contra-fan engine (developed in years 1980s ; BPR around 20) tested in December 2016 with redesigned blades, and a European one (BPR around 16) which was expected to be tested in 2018¹⁹.

More radical and promising concepts for longer term possible applications (TRL1-3)

More radical but less mature solutions, able to provide fuel burn / CO₂ reductions, must absolutely be explored in order to concretely achieve ACARE CO₂ 2020 goal and then progress further towards 2050 goal.

At engine level, the European ULTIMATE project investigated a large number of such disruptive solutions, at TRL2. Some solutions could offer substantial reductions, but some barriers must be overcome. For instance inter-cooling requires minimizing heat exchanger weight and associated pressure losses ; Isochoric combustion (with various possible options) would permit a significant improvement of the engine thermal efficiency, but specific technical issues need to be solved in particular: the interaction with the turbine, mechanical and thermal challenges, possible pollutant issues linked to the way the combustion is performed ; inter-turbine burning which could give some NO_x advantage and potential efficiency gain (and could possibly ease the use of 2 fuels) , must also be matured... The ULTIMATE project ended in 2018 (the last FORUM-AE CO₂ workshop took place

¹⁹ Although some encouraging results were presented at the FORUM-AE CO₂ workshop beginning of 2017, for the new design of the NK-93 engine (6.45% sfc reduction over the 1980s NK-93 original configuration, together with noise Chapter 14 compliance), it seems that the project didn't provide definitive conclusions on the benefit of a contra-rotating turbofan, and the European concept was assessed only by CFD, without any demonstrator

beginning of 2017), and provided rich results which are described more in details in [1] & [23]. Some emphasis is put in particular on the significant thermal efficiency gain of pressure rise combustion.

Figure 14: ULTIMATE: "Boxprop" concept – Chalmers (left) and MTU IRA engine (right)

At aircraft level, pursuing the old European NACRE project (on innovative aircraft configurations), the new NACOR (New Innovative Aircraft Configurations) project was launched in 2016 in the Clean Sky 2 Airframe ITD, but little dissemination was performed up to now. However, rich information was shared inside FORUM-AE, in particular coming from Cranfield or TU-Delft universities, which show that many ideas are explored. A comprehensive review, synthesizing a large volume of studies, some in collaboration with Airbus, Boeing or Nasa, was provided by Cranfield University during the second CO₂ mitigation workshop (Reims, May 2017). It includes in particular Blended Wing Body aircraft concepts, LNG aircraft (A321 like target application), hybrid electric propulsion aircraft. It is important to stress that these concepts may require many innovations, which may be key enablers. Although evaluation is done at relatively low maturity level, the current estimation shows significant CO₂ reduction potential.

Figure 15: Disruptive aircraft concepts studies at Cranfield

During the same workshop, more details were provided by TU-Delft on a combined kerosene/LNG aircraft designed for short and medium range application (A320 reference). The selected configuration adopts the same choice as in Cranfield study on the LNG tank location under the wing. Necessity of combining 2 fuels (which requires 2 fuels systems and induces therefore more complexity and weight) may be questioned. It is recognized that LNG solution is a major change, involving in addition significant infrastructure adaptation at airport level, but it is based on existing technology and looks therefore rather attractive.

Figure 16: Kerosene/LNG aircraft (with Open Rotor) study at TU-Delft (left); Russian TU 155 experimental cryogenic aircraft - 1980s (right)

Aircraft electric hybridization is seen by some ones as a promising solution to mitigate the fuel burn, and the CO₂ emissions. There are many hybridization options, but in all cases, it concerns both the propulsion system and the aircraft. Effectively, the propulsion system will combine energy coming from fuel and from electricity source, and the aircraft will have to carry simultaneously fuel and batteries (or fuel cells); at aircraft level, specific hybrid management of non propulsive and propulsive energy is also necessary.

Fundamentals on electric hybridization were recalled by Safran, who introduces 2 degrees of hybridization, in power and in energy. New (Clean Sky 2) NOVAIR project, coordinateded by NLR, illustrates the motivation on the subject. As fuel cells (FC) are an alternative to batteries for electrical energy storage, state of the art was recalled by Bauhaus Luftfahrt. Polymer Electric Fuel Cells (PEFC) seem promising; technical barriers must be considered such as cooling of the FC, getting rid of water produced, volume of FC... A first step may be considering replacing the APU by a FC. In case that fuel cells power the entire on-board systems, prospects of fuel burn reduction are less than 3% for a mid-range aircraft.

Figure 17: Degrees of hybridization of investigated concepts (Safran overview)

The hybridization topic raises important discussion. It appears in particular, that the benefit of hybridization will depend strongly on the electrical energy and power density assumptions, which should be realistic even if extrapolated in the future. If a high degree of hybridization is envisaged, supra-conductivity becomes also a major enabler. Also, the CO₂ budget is directly linked to electricity

LCA CO₂ hypothesis. As NOVAIR targeted a flight demonstrator in 2020²⁰, objective of such a demonstrator was questioned and scalability issue could be encountered.

Project's view is that electric hybridization of the aircraft is possibly promising, but still at low maturity level for regional and short/medium range applications and with a moderate CO₂ reduction potential; smaller aircraft appear indeed an easier application target, for a stepped approach.

Not necessarily relying on revolutionary aircraft or engine technology, substantial reduction of fuel burn / CO₂ is assessed by DLR considering jointly optimized aircraft operation with optimized aircraft design. In that spirit, the Intermediate Stop Operation (ISO) approach (long range missions are performed in few steps of ~3000nm and the aircraft is designed for this smaller range) gives interesting results. The exercise done on B777 and A330 fleet (with 2 redesigned configurations and ISO option when appropriate) gives ~11% CO₂ reduction. Addressing aviation climate impact, it may be more relevant to minimize the Average Temperature Response (ATR) which depends not only on emitted CO₂ but also on contrails formation and NO_x emission. In that prospect the DLR Compatible Air Transport System (CATS) approach, suggests to fly lower and slower but with an aircraft redesigned for this new flight specifications. By this approach, without Cash Operating Cost (COC) increase, an ATR reduction of ~30% is estimated for a redesigned A320.

Figure 18: DLR CATS assessment: ATR/COC trade-off

Clean Sky achievements above TRL5-6 and perspectives

Clean Sky 1 (CS1) projects, including SAGE (Sustainable And Green Engines) bunch of projects represent a huge effort to mature technology up to TRL5-6, with most often the help of important demonstrators. This major technological effort is now pursued in Clean Sky 2 (CS2).

In SAGE frame, Safran Aircraft Engines delivered a Contra Rotating Open Rotor (CROR) demonstrator. This is a pusher configuration, with composite blades propellers; it is a geared design contrarily to the GE36 UDF tested in years 80s, and it was carefully designed to minimize noise (it is estimated to pass Chapt. 14). Many technological obstacles (rear part fully rotating, oil system & cooling, control law...) were solved and the campaign in Istres (south of France), initiated in June 2017 was successfully completed in December 2017, demonstrating the ability to operate the engine on the full power range. A complete overview of the design and demonstration was published in 2019 (ref. [25]).

²⁰ Now postponed to 2021

Figure 19: Safran Aircraft Engines CS1 SAGE CROR demonstrator and Istres installation

Rolls-Royce performed major developments inside CS1 SAGE, complemented with UK or German funding, supporting their roadmap towards a so called “UltraFan” family (3 shafts, with gearbox, high pressure core with lean burn combustion, pitched fan, CMC turbine components). Among major developments, the composite fan blades demonstrator ALPS²¹ was tested on the ground and in flight.

Figure 20: Rolls Royce CS1 SAGE ALPS flight demonstration (left) and CMC HT3 demo (right)

For helicopter engines, the Tech 800 turbine demonstrator (now introduced in the design of the new Arrano engine) was developed and tested by Safran Helicopter Engines. It is estimated that a 15% fuel burn reduction was achieved at TRL5 compared to year 2000. In Clean Sky 2, a small Turbo-Prop based on an Ardiden turbine will be investigated with an objective of 20% CO₂ reduction. Specific work on propeller blades by Onera was expected in CS2 ANTARES project.

Figure 21: Safran Helicopter Engines CS1 SAGE Tech 800 (left) and CS2 Turbo Prop project (right)

²¹ Advanced Low Pressure System demonstrator inside CS1-SAGE3

Natural Laminar Flow (NLF) should permit to reduce the aircraft drag and consequently the fuel burn and the CO₂. This solution was well explored by Airbus in BLADE project²² of Clean Sky 1 SFWA (Smart Fixed Wing Aircraft) ITD. Onera was also very active on this subject in Clean sky 1 GRA (Green Regional Aircraft) ITD. NLF was assessed experimentally and numerically on regional aircraft wing, designed for NLF ; up to 6% CO₂ reduction was estimated for a 130 pax regional aircraft configuration with NLF wings and rear mounted engines. However, it appears (as analysed by DLR who shows the effect of insects' impacts), that NLF requires a very high surface quality.

Figure 22: CS1 GRA NLF investigation – Onera (left) ; Environmental factor modeling – DLR (right)

Knowing Clean Sky 1 supported work on manufacturing & recycling (Eco-Design ITD), it is recognized that it contributes only weakly to the CO₂ budget and the concern is more on toxicity of certain products used for manufacturing, or typical recyclability issues.

Overall assessment of technologies and concepts developed in Clean Sky 1, was assessed by Clean Sky Technology Evaluator (CS-TE) under the lead of DLR. This exercise which requires a well defined methodology is essential to judge the combined benefit of all technologies and concepts. In the case of Short and Medium Range (SMR) aircraft, assuming Open Rotor, NLF and flight optimisation, a reduction of 41% is estimated compared to year 2000 (A320 reference). At Air Transport System level, assuming Clean Sky 1 technology fully included in 2020 global fleet, the CO₂ reduction would be 32%. This is of course an optimistic scenario, but it gives the potentiality from Clean Sky technology.

Up-dated assessment of progress towards ACARE CO₂ goal

A previous assessment was published in the Mid-Term synthesis report (2015). The exercise is difficult, as it requires evaluating both CO₂ mitigation potential and extrapolated maturity in 2020, for various categories of aircraft, which may incorporate large panel of innovative technologies or choose between different types of architectures. When calculating the mitigation potential, it depends also on the year 2000 reference in the same aircraft category.

With all these reserves, and conciliating the various inputs (LEMCOTEC/E-BREAK/ENOVAL, CS-TE, NLF studies) and assuming again (as in 2015 mid-term assessment) a 7% reduction from flight optimisation, FORUM-AE vision in 2017 was that the following FB / CO₂ reductions were achievable in 2020 at TRL5-6:

²² Flight demonstration was realised end of 2017 with exploitation in 2018 ; results presented at AEC 2020 conference gave confidence in achieving up to 5% fuel burn reduction thanks to natural laminarity

Category (aircraft)	Average perspective			
	Regional (TP)	Regional (TF)	Short and Medium Range	Long range
Reference	ATR72	E-180	A320	A330
CO2 reduction main basis	new TP, lighter, NLF	GTF, NLF, lighter	CROR, NLF, lighter	SAGE3 or GTF, NLF, lighter
% CO2 reduction	down to 27	down to 27	[38%, 41%]	[19%, 26%]
Comments	Improvements from mission optimisation also included			

Table 5: CO₂ reduction estimated ranges from new technology introduction (from Clean Sky & FP7)

3.1.2 Recommendations and needs

The following key statements and recommendations were done by FORUM-AE in 2017.

- 1) In general, CO₂ mitigation solutions at aircraft and engine levels will rely on better aircraft aerodynamics (including better propulsion system integration to the aircraft), smaller weights, higher thermal and propulsive efficiencies of the engine, possibly new engine cycles, and possibly more favorable mission specification. New energy carriers (drop-in fuels, LNG, electrical source...) may play also a role in the future²³.
- 2) Projects like E-BREAK, LEMCOTEC, ENOVAL (FP7 “Level 2” projects) together with CLEAN SKY projects contribute efficiently to mature well identified technologies and architectures with clear CO₂ reduction potential, up to TRL5-6. Feasibility of some concepts relies on key technological enablers which may still require some demonstration.
- 3) Since previous assessment (FORUM-AE Mid-Term Synthesis in 2015), the progress towards ACARE 2020 CO₂ goal is mainly in terms of technology maturity. Nevertheless, reduction potential achievable at TRL5-6 in the horizon 2020 was consolidated. This exercise remains complicated and must be done for each aircraft category. **This new assessment shows, despite progress, that currently the ACARE 2020 CO₂ goal will not be met²⁴.** The highest mitigation potential demonstrated at TRL5-6 is obtained for a short and medium range aircraft equipped with a CROR, assuming Natural Laminar Flow wings and optimized trajectory.
- 4) For longer term applications, it is clear that **disruptive solutions are necessary to achieve H2020 CO₂ goal (-50% kg/pass km) and to progress further towards H2050 CO₂ goal (-75% kg/pass km).** Indeed, a very rich panel of low TRL solutions exists (see dedicated workshops proceedings). ULTIMATE project illustrates the kind of promising radical solutions at engine level. All these solutions deserve to be investigated²⁵.
- 5) Among them, electric hybridization of the aircraft is a possibly promising route but still at low TRL. Actual CO₂ reduction potential will depend fundamentally on electric energy/power densities, supra-conductivity applicability and sustainable electricity availability with good CO₂ LCA budget. Also, large number of hybridization options exist. Another attractive solution is an LNG aircraft; it is a radical change but it relies mainly on existing technology, and would offer substantial CO₂ reduction.

²³ but their expected benefit would come before all from their possible advantageous LCA CO₂ budget whereas aircraft/engine energy efficiency improvement with these new energy carriers may not be better.

²⁴ Currently, in 2020, we confirm this statement

²⁵ Disruptive solutions were also investigated by European AHEAD project (see [39])

- 6) Combined aircraft/flight optimisation could also permit CO₂ reduction, even with existing technology. This may be the case of Intermediate Stop Option (ISO) strategy, or when flying lower & slower ; however, a new practice such as ISO may have some drawbacks (more landings and take-offs, more flight disturbance, possibly higher operating costs...) to be duly addressed.

Lastly, renewable sustainable drop-in fuels, offer additional means to permit CO₂ mitigation, at the condition that there is sufficient available volume at global scale (ps: see more complete statements in §3.4).

3.2 Non-CO₂ emissions Technological mitigation (combustion)

3.2.1 General Status

The content of this synthesis is based on workshop technical contributions with induced discussions, and possible further iterations after the workshop. It includes main results, provides assessment on the progress towards ACARE NO_x goals, complemented with qualitative statements on ultrafine particles and their mitigation. Lastly, it gives a list of key statements together with recommendations on relevant RTD orientations.

Context and ACARE non-CO₂ Goals

The reduction of non-CO₂ emissions, principally NO_x and ultra-fine particles, is justified both by air quality and climate change concerns. As an answer, there exist international ICAO standards for engines addressing NO_x (with regular increase of stringency) and since 2016 for ultra-fine particles (with an application date after 1st January 2020). Taxes at airports on NO_x emissions, provide also some incentive for their reduction.

In that context, the Advisory Council for Aeronautics Research in Europe (ACARE) has fixed very challenging NO_x goals reductions (Vision 2020 and Flight Path 2050) for research and technology development European programs, applying on aircraft technology, engine technology and aircraft operations. No quantitative goals have been defined for particles, because it was a newer subject at the time, but the need to better know particles emissions from aircraft engines and reduce them is clearly recognized in the ACARE SRIA (ref. [4]). Assessment of this RTD effort was one of the tasks of FORUM-AE project. The following table recalls the mid-term assessment performed by FORUM-AE in 2015.

	Reference 2000	ACARE 2020 Goals (at TRL6)		ACARE 2050 Goals (at TRL6)		FORUM-AE Assessment (2015) (extrapol. at TRL6 in 2020)
		High Level	detailed (SRA)	High Level	detailed (SRIA)	
CO2	<i>Representative technology of aircraft & engine with 2000 EIS, & representative 2000 ATM</i>	"-50% per pass km"	aircraft: -20% to -25% engine: -15% to -20% ATM: -5% to -10%	"-75% per pass km"	aircraft & engine: -68% ATM: -12% Other: -12%	aircraft + engine +ATM: ≈ -38% in average per pass km
NOx (LTO)		"-80%"	engine: -60% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	"-90%"	engine: -75% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	engine: [-55%, -65%] CAEP6
NOx (Cruise)		"-80%"	Achieved through -50% Fuel Burn & -60% cruise EINOx reduction	"-90%"	Achieved through -75% Fuel Burn & further cruise EINOx reduction	not quantified
Other emissions		"damaging emissions reduced"	emissions qualitatively reduced (particules, CO, UHC) and better understanding of impacts	"emissions-free taxiing" + qualitative reduction	knowlegde of emissions (particules, VOC) and better understanding of impacts	better knowledge of engines particles emissions

Table 6: Recall of ACARE 2020 & 2050 Goals and FORUM-AE mid-term assessment

Particles issue

Back-ground on particles:

Soot is formed in the primary zone of the combustor in rich zones at temperatures between 1000-1500K and is oxidised in the downstream part of the combustor. Both production and oxidation processes involve a huge number of particles and complex chemical pathways, so are difficult to measure and model.

Truly predictive methods for soot particle size distribution should be derived covering the full range of operating conditions, from idle to take-off. In that prospect:

- Validations on higher pressure and temperature rigs are required.
- Size distributions predictions should be compared with engine exhaust measurements.
- Predictive methods should be developed, which have to show an appropriate trade off between accuracy and computational cost for use in industry.
- The link between fuel preparation and soot concentration and particle size distribution should be investigated for pressures going from idle to take-off. Different chemical reactions and pathways may be dominant for different conditions in terms of pressure, temperature and air-fuel-ratio.
- Fuels used should be representative/applicable to kerosene chemistry
- Validated soot reaction mechanisms should include emphasis on oxidation rates noting the reactivity of different black carbon structures.

Experimental diagnostics on particles:

Strong and key expertise (in particular at DLR and Onera) was developed thanks to a series of European projects (Sia-Team, TLC, FIRST, now SOPRANO) and is still pursued. Advanced optical measurements in more representative conditions (in particular for pressure) provide rich information. A good overview was provided in the two dedicated workshops (in 2014 & 2017) and disseminated at CAEP technology reviews in Munich (2014) and Washington (2017).

Figure 23: « FIRST » injector & LII measurements at DLR (left) ; « TLC » particles size measurements at Onera on multi-point injection system (right)

Certification like measurements behind engines:

Important contribution to ICAO new nvPM (non volatile Particulate Matter) standards establishment was performed by European manufacturers, in particular thanks to European Commission funded campaigns (MOVE/C2/SER/2014-269/SI2.706115) and some national projects²⁶.

Issue of diffusion loss in the existing measurement protocol was raised and could deserve some investigation. However, the protocol was concerned by the fact that all manufacturers perform measurements in the same manner.

Figure 24: Rolls-Royce measurements (left) & Safran Aircraft Engines measurements (right) (EC funded campaigns in 2015 & 2016)

Technological status from major European programs (TRL4-5)

General status:

Rolls-Royce, SAFRAN-AE, GE-AVIO low emission combustion technology development, is supported by European funded projects like LEMCOTEC, by smaller projects of the Low Emission Combustor

²⁶ French DGAC Mermose project on PowerJet SaM146 engine ; German Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure on RRD engine

Technology “LECT” cluster of projects (IMPACT-AE, SOPRANO...), by the Clean Sky 1 ALECSYS project (for RR-UK) and by national projects. Most of the focus is put on lean combustion.

Figure 25: Low Emission Combustor Technology European projects (on-going or recently completed projects in 2017 are indicated)

Up-dated assessment of Rolls-Royce/SAFRAN-AE/GE-AVIO lean combustion technology ²⁷ development (in terms of NO_x reduction levels & technology maturity) confirms mostly the previous FORUM-AE assessment done in 2015 (see table 6), with some improvement on the estimated achievable CAEP6 margin range (now ≈ [-60%;-70%]).

Status concerning LTO NO_x (see Figures hereafter), is based principally on LEMCOTEC assessment (See Ref. [19]). It is assumed that the investigated combustor technology is put on an engine with significantly increased efficiency. CAEP6 is taken as reference, in phase with ACARE SRIA Vol.1.

Figure 26: Performance status in the DP/NO_x=f(OPR) diagram showing also reference engines

²⁷ Respectively called LDI (Lean direct Injection), MSFI (Multiple Staged Fuel Injection), PERM (partially evaporating and rapid mixing)

Figure 27: Technology maturity status for the different lean burn technologies (PERM/MSFI/LDI) developed in LEMCOTEC

Status concerning cruise (or mission) NO_x comes from the Clean Sky Technology Evaluator (CS-TE). The reductions levels are estimated by comparing two similar missions between an aircraft/engine Clean Sky solution and a reference aircraft/engine solution representative of year 2000. The estimated reduction may vary with the aircraft category and depends not only on the combustion technology, but also on the engine architecture and on the improved aircraft performances. Considering a SMR aircraft with an Open Rotor equipped with lean burn combustor technology, the mission NO_x reduction is estimated at ~42%. But there is an important uncertainty, linked in particular to the fact that cruise EINO_x for lean combustion is poorly estimated. When targeting more specifically the combustor technology, it could be relevant to look at the cruise EINO_x (as a function of OPR) to really measure its NO_x performance, independently of the aircraft/engine efficiency.

Clean Sky concept aircraft	NO _x
Short-medium range - Open rotor engine	-42%
Long Range - 3 shaft Advanced Turbo-fan	-39%
TP 90 Regional - Turbo-prop	-46%
GTF 130 Regional - Geared Turbo-fan	-38%

Table 7: CS1-TE mission NO_x assessment

Induced observations:

Following observations are based on experience gained in European programs and on consensus from FORUM-AE workshops. Both nvPM (in mass and number) and NO_x need to be reduced simultaneously (as already stressed in 2014 workshop). The leading solution in European projects for low emissions is lean burn technology which remains a revolutionary step in combustion technology development. At high power it is expected to mitigate both nvPM (mass, and probably number) and NO_x.

Implementation of lean combustion on small thrust engines may however raise some difficulties, either because of the small combustor size or the small OPR often encountered (but not always) for this category of engines. Consequently, dedicated technologies (e.g. additive layer manufacturing)

might be required to make it feasible. In the contrary, there is still room for rich burn technology on smaller engines, with improvements (with up to ~20% further NO_x reduction compared to current in-service rich burn technology as evaluated by RR). In that case, there is inevitably some trade between NO_x and nvPM.

Figure 28: NO_x/nvPM trade-off for RQL combustion technology (schematic)

The choice of combustion technology (lean/rich) may be also influenced by the engine cycle (mainly OPR & T₄₁) and possibly by operability constraints (for instance, higher altitude relight capability).

All combustion technologies (lean/rich) involve the need to improve:

- the fuel injection technology:
 - Better atomisation
 - Reduced risk of fuel coking...
- the cooling efficiency in order to maintain mixing air control for RQL systems or to increase the % of air introduced through the injection system for lean burn systems.
 - Improved manufacturing (e.g. Additive Layer Manufacturing)
 - Improved materials (CMCs or better metals)
 - Porosity pattern optimisation...

Lastly, staged combustion solutions (which may be relevant for lean approach but also for improved rich approach) involve important enabling technologies outside the immediate combustion sphere:

- Engine control is important for staging
- The staged fuel system needs fully proving
- Combustion acoustic understanding and control is required

More radical concepts for longer term possible applications (TRL1-3)

Isochoric combustion:

This new type of combustion is realized in concepts such as CVC (Constant Volume Combustion), RDE (Rotative Detonation Engines), PDE (Pulsed Detonation Engines). It is promising in terms of engine cycle thermal efficiency (Humphrey cycle instead of Brayton cycle) but is still at low maturity. Demonstrated gains by the simulation of a single CVC module go up to -20% sfc (but it depends on the type of application: turboshaft, turboprop, OPR range...).

Many challenges must be addressed to achieve sufficient maturity and reach the SFC targeted gains such as:

- Technological solution to minimize efficiency losses due to leakage at combustor inlet & outlet and combustor cooling systems
- Turbine performance with high unsteady level of inlet flows

Concerning pollutant emissions, high level production is a critical risk, in particular:

- For NO_x, due to high gas temperature during combustion phase
- For CO & UHC due to complete combustion being difficult to achieve

In that prospect, improvement means should be investigated such as:

- Exhaust gas recirculation to manage combustion gas temperature
- Fuel injection / air mixing / turbulence level during combustion phase

Other “alternative combustions”:

Other low TRL interesting concepts such as flameless combustion, sequential combustion (turbine stage between two combustors) and Trap Vortex Combustion (TVC) deserve also interest.

Advanced investigation methods

Lean combustion technology development (design & optimisation) is fundamentally based on advance experimental & numerical methods.

Experimental methods (as deployed at DLR, Onera, Coria, Patras Univ., Florence Univ., Sheffield Univ., Cranfield Univ.;... this list being not exhaustive) rely on a large range of measurements techniques, with many optical ones, and on test capacities sufficiently representative of future combustors operating conditions. They permit to provide data for numerical methods and to address key topics for manufacturers:

- Atomisation & Fuel placement (shadowgraphy, PLIF-fuel)
- Reaction zone structure (PLIF-OH, PLIF-CO, PLIF-NO)
- Soot formation (improved LII, sampling & advanced characterization)
- Temperature profiles (CARS, FRS)
- Altitude relight (fast camera)...

Numerical prediction for combustion relies more and more on LES approach, which is able to solve correctly the interaction between turbulence and chemistry. Increased focus is done to better take into account effect of fuel composition on combustion and to improve soot prediction.

- As lean combustion technology is more prone to instabilities, special emphasis is done both in experimental and numerical investigation, to better anticipate them.

Figure 29: DLR Optical Swirling Spray Injector (OSSI): Single point jet in crossflow; Shadowgraphy - Average intensity of 150 shots

Figure 30: Onera PLIF diagnosis on MSFI system; Super-imposition of Fuel (colour) & OH (grey scale)

Figure 31: CORIA HERON high pressure rig and flame structure investigation by fuel & OH PLIF

Figure 32: Florence Univ. – Effusion cooling investigation; exp (left) & numerical (right)

Up-dated assessment of progress towards ACARE non-CO2 goal

A previous assessment was published in the Mid-Term synthesis report (2015). Using partly LEMCOTEC and Clean Sky inputs, consolidated status has been done and FORUM-AE vision in 2017 was that the following NOx reductions at airport level (air quality concern based on LTO cycle) and at cruise level (climate change concern) seemed achievable in 2020 at TRL5-6:

Combustor technology	PERM	MSFI	LDI
Aircraft application target	Regional	Short & Medium Range	Long Range
Engine application assumption	GTF	CROR	UHBPR TF
OPR assumption (T/O)	36	45	61
Current Maturity (TRL)	~5	~5	~5-6
Margin to CAEP6 *	-71,0%	-65,3%	-63,7%
Mission reduction from y2000 **	-38,0%	-42,0%	-39,0%

* based on LEMCOTEC assessment ; CAEP6 is taken as the reference, in phase with ACARE SRIA Vol. 1

** based on CS-TE assessment but strong uncertainties because NOx is poorly extrapolated in cruise for lean burn techno

Table 8: NOx status for the different lean burn technologies developed in European RTD projects

3.2.2 Recommendations and needs

The following key statements and recommendations are proposed by FORUM-AE.

- 1) A new and final assessment towards ACARE NO_x goals consolidates the provisional mid-term assessment. Assuming it is combined with a significant engine efficiency improvement, the investigated lean combustion technology should permit to go beyond 2020 ACARE NO_x goal and to achieve good progress towards 2050 goal at airports (LTO cycle). In this new assessment, and despite strong uncertainties, evaluation is proposed also at cruise level; in that case, ACARE NO_x 2020 goal is not fully achieved. Nevertheless TRL5 is barely achieved for some engine categories, and further maturation is mandatory.
- 2) As already stressed during the first non-CO₂ workshop (in 2014), European manufacturers agree to the need that future combustion technology should simultaneously reduce NO_x emissions and ultrafine particles (more precisely non volatile Particulate Matter – nvPM). Ultrafine particles are a newer topic and there is therefore critical work to be done on better physics understanding, on modeling and on measurements.
- 3) It is recognized that lean combustion is the most appropriate way to reduce both NO_x and particles. However the precise combustion technology strategy may depend on the different kinds of applications. In particular, advanced rich burn combustion may be still required for some advanced small (thrust) engines or for legacy products improvements.
- 4) Whatever the strategy adopted, some investigation priorities are well identified (among them, staged combustion, instabilities control, particles mass & number mitigation...) and for that the support of experimental/numerical diagnostics is essential.
- 5) Alternative combustion technology solutions at much lower maturity and with some associated risks, such as isochoric combustion, deserve interest.
- 6) Lastly, optimized fuel composition (either fossil or renewable sustainable ones), offers additional means for nvPM mitigation, if it is feasible to increase the H/C ratio (by lower aromatic content).

3.3 Operational mitigation

3.3.1 General status

Ability to improve the aircraft operations, by flight trajectory optimisation, improved air traffic management, airport specific actions, better operational practices etc... could be implemented rather rapidly, contrarily to new and promising technology development which requires often more than one decade anticipation. Knowing emitted CO₂ effect on earth temperature in 2100 is integrated since the instant of emission, then the earlier CO₂ emissions may be avoided, the better.

Few European projects on operational aspects are on-going or recently completed (see table below). SESAR Joint Under-taking, is of course a major one. Safety and capacity are probably the two main

topics addressed by SESAR but a part of it is dedicated to CO₂ mitigation. Also it may appear that some ATM solutions proposed for other purposes, may be beneficial for CO₂, such as AMAN (Arrival MANagement systems). In 2016, it was estimated in SESAR, that 2.8% CO₂ mitigation through operational improvements was achievable in 2020, with the top five solutions for it being described in table 10. However, initial objective of SESAR was to demonstrate 10% reduction, in agreement with ACARE 2020 goal ATM share, and this effort is still pursued.

PROJECT	T0	Coordinator	TITLE
SESAR 1	2007	JU	Single European Sky ATM Research
SESAR/IMET	2011	NLR	Investigating the optimal approach for future trajectory prediction systems to use METeorological uncertainty information
SESAR 2020	2014	JU	SESAR 1 follow-up
SESAR/ATM4E	2015	DLR*	Air Traffic Management for Environment
CleanSky - SGO	2008	Thales	System for Green Operation
AIRE	2009	SJU-FAA	Atlantic Interoperability Initiative to Reduce Emissions
RECREATE	2007	NLR	REsearch on a CRuiser – Enabled Air Transport Environment
ERAT	2007	To70	Environmental Responsible Air Transport

Table 9: main European projects on Aircraft Operations and ATM, in 2017

When considering city pair flights, there is still margin of progress in terms of **trajectory optimisation**. If priority is put on CO₂ reduction, one can identify some possible obstacles and also enablers. Among obstacles, one can mention the route charges (as soon as they are not uniform, longer flight may be logically chosen by companies to minimize operating costs) or the time to arrival target practice combined with delays at departures (in that case, flight speed will be higher than usual at the expense of fuel burn). But many enabling solutions are identified (in European projects like AIRE and SATISFIED and also in national studies) such as 3D trajectory optimisation with efficient softwares, better weather forecast and flight planning taking into account weather forecast uncertainty, improved flight management systems (FMS). Optimal trajectory focus would permit to reduce CO₂ between 1% to 4%, compared to current situation.

<p>Optimised 2D/3D Routes (-0.78%): The contribution to the Fuel efficiency KPA has increased significantly in compare to the results last year owing to inclusion of validation results for Advanced RNP Operations in En-Route in high complexity airspace. The confidence level for this assessment result is however Low.</p>
<p>Free Routing provides a significant contribution (-0.44%) by reducing flown distance and flight time. There has been a small, improved contribution from re-assessment of results this year. The interaction between Free Routing and Airspace Management and AFUA needs to be reviewed, as does the compatibility Free Routing and the benefits in En-Route of Optimised 2D/3D Routes. The confidence level was set High.</p>
<p>Airport Operations Management (-0.30%): There has been a significant improvement in the fuel efficiency benefit assessment compare to last year validation results. Most of the benefits are observed at high complexity airport from reduced holding and deviation of arriving traffic during peaks, reduced conflicts between arrival and departure traffic on stand and aprons and reduction in waiting times for the de-icing process. The Confidence Level for this assessment result was set Low due to lack of validation results.</p>
<p>Integrated Surface Management (-0.22%): This concept optimises taxi times and increases fuel efficiency by 0.22% in high and medium density airports through the integration of route generation with the planning information as well as through enhanced guidance services such as Airfield Ground Lighting (AGL). Approximately 21000 flights are expected to be impacted saving 17kg of fuel each. The confidence level is Medium.</p>
<p>Enhanced Runway Throughput: (-0.08%). Time Based Separation Real Time Simulation have demonstrated fuel savings of 43kg per flight at Heathrow¹³. Benefits but have to be extrapolated across the limited restricted set of hubs likely to deploy the concept. RECAT and Weather Dependent Separation (WDS-A/D) (Dynamic Wake Vortex OIs) have also shown fuel saving by reducing the airborne holding and at departure by reducing the taxi out queuing. The confidence level for this assessment result is Medium.</p>
<p>The overall confidence levels of the contributing OFAs for the Fuel Efficiency KPA give the overall confidence level Medium.</p>

Table 10: SESAR top 5 solutions for CO₂ mitigation

Of course, more accurate flight planning with better prediction of the fuel volume (including mandatory extra fuel for safety reason) to perform a flight between a city pair will be beneficial for

CO₂ reduction. And operational practices, where more fuel than needed to perform a city pair direct flight is carried, should be clearly avoided²⁸.

If now flight optimisation is performed not considering only CO₂ but also non-CO₂ emissions indirect effect on climate (such as NO_x or contrails/contrail-cirrus effects), the problem becomes more complicated. Interesting idea of **Climate Change Functions** (CCF) is developed by DLR (see [36] & [37]), which is a way to realise a multi-criteria trajectory optimisation.

Figure 33: SATISFIED European project – Routes on which optimization exercise was performed

More aggressive solutions exist. The Intermediate Stop Operations (ISO) approach, already considered in the Greener by Design report [9] and more recently evaluated by DLR [40], suggests to cut long travel flights in smaller ones (of around 2500nm range) thanks to intermediate stops. Implemented with existing aircraft and possibly some adaptation of the airports global network, could possibly permit a reduction between 5 to 15% CO₂. ISO approach with redesigned aircraft (design range closer to 2500nm), would boost the benefit between 13 to 23%. However, ISO approach (with existing or dedicated aircraft) may generate more NO_x and CO/UHC emissions at airports. This ISO trade-off should be kept in mind. Fleet Optimisation (“FLOP”) could be also an alternative to be evaluated: more optimal use of the existing fleet would increase its average energy efficiency. Going further, with redesigned aircraft on more focused operational ranges, the fleet average efficiency would be even higher. Of course, this would induce also a trade with fleet flexibility. Lastly, one can mention the Air to Air Refueling (AAR) solution as assessed in RECREATE European project, which may appear much more complicated in terms of implementation.

At airport level, many specific solutions are already well identified, and may be more largely deployed, even if it is already the case at some airports: Collaborative Decision Making (CDM), Continuous Descent Operation (CDO), taxi-time reduction, Aircraft Ground Energy Systems (AGES) use, greener taxiing practices (EGTS, Taxi-bot, 1 engine upon 2 operated) as studied for instance at Zurich airport²⁹.

²⁸ This includes tankering practice

²⁹ Flughafen Zürich AG: Alternative Aircraft Taxi Systems: Effects on local air quality. December 2013 (not published)

Figure 34: AGES use at Zurich Airport

3.3.2 Recommendations and needs

The following key statements and recommendations are done by FORUM-AE.

- 1) Flights and ATM should be still improved to fill the important remaining gap to achieve the ACARE 2020 CO₂ reduction goal target allocated to operational means (about -10%)
- 2) With more disruptive operational solutions, such as Intermediate Stop Operations (ISO) with associated redesigned aircraft, it looks feasible to obtain further reduction.
- 3) Specific solutions at airports are rather well identified, such as Aircraft Ground Energy Systems (AGES) use and greener taxiing practices, and their deployment should be encouraged.

3.4 Perspective of Renewable Fuels

3.4.1 General Status:

- Harmonisation **was still needed in 2017 to converge on a common and technically satisfactory CO₂ LCA methodology** in order to assess the reduction potential of alternative jet fuel³⁰ production pathways ; this harmonisation was carried out by AFTF³¹ ; In addition, it was necessary to check that these pathways meet the European RED³² requirement. The following figure gives the aviation CO₂ with different scenarios, without the help of alternative fuel. We can calculate that with the very optimistic ACARE 2050 scenario, and

³⁰ Referred now as Sustainable Alternative Fuels (SAF)

³¹ AFTF = ICAO Alternative Fuel Task Force

³² Renewable Energy Directive (Directive 2009/28/EC now replaced by Directive (EU) 2018/2001)

assuming a CO₂ LCA budget from alternative fuels of 80%, around **300 Mt** would be necessary to have aviation CO₂ emissions divided by two in 2050 compared to 2005.

« ACARE 2050 vision » hypothesis: objective of -75% CO₂/km/pass in 2050 compared to 2000 is achieved and corresponding technology is fully introduced in 2050 fleet ; one assumes a continuous improvement of average efficiency till 2050 ; « ICAO vision » hypothesis: constant efficiency gain of 2% is assumed till 2020 and is followed by Carbon Neutral Growth ; Hypothesis for all scenarii: ICAO 2018 long term average air traffic growth of 4.1% is taken

Figure 35: CO₂ extrapolation till 2050 without alternative fuels

- Various experimental results show that reducing the aromatic content in jet fuel induces a significant reduction of non volatile particles. This trend is confirmed by physical analysis and modelling. Therefore, from the environmental point of view, either considering air quality or climate change, **it is recommended to minimize as much as possible the aromatic content of future jet fuels.** Although less material was presented on the topic of sulphur content, it is believed also that reducing jet fuel sulphur content is environmentally beneficial, as it should reduce volatile particles.

Fig. 36: Illustration on a CFM56 turbofan of fuel effect on non volatile particles (AAFEX II)

- Optimisation of future jet fuels composition has become an emerging topic.** It is true both for future renewable drop-in jet fuels and for fossil jet-A1 evolution. This optimization could permit to minimize particles and possibly other pollutant emissions. Although less obvious, it could also potentially permit to improve the fuel compatibility with the engine and the aircraft fuel system or even improve engine performances.

Fig. 37: Kinetic models of various fuels to predict combustion & emissions (Polimi)

- Improvement of the modelling of fuel interaction with the engine, and development of predictive tools is necessary.** It could be applied to various fuel/engine or fuel/fuel system interactions like material compatibility, viscosity effects, thermal stability, etc. Therefore, modelling ability is a prerequisite to permit the fuel optimization and in addition it will help, accelerate and reduce the cost of ASTM³³ international certification process.

Figure 38: Existing models for viscosity of pure products (IFPEN)

³³ American Society for Testing Material

Figure 39: Monodisperse Spray Evaporation Modeling : Isopropanol (DLR)

3.4.2 Recommendations and needs

- 1) Harmonisation should be pursued to converge on a common and technically satisfactory CO₂ LCA methodology in order to assess alternative jet fuel production pathways.
- 2) The aromatic content of future jet fuels (fossil or renewable) should be minimized as much as possible in order to reduce particles emission. Reduction of sulphur content is also beneficial and should be encouraged, knowing that for fossil fuels, the sulphur reduction process generally leads to less aromatics.
- 3) Work, such as the one supported by the on-going JETSCREEN³⁴ European project, to develop predictive tools to model the fuel interaction with the aircraft fuel system or with the engine, should be carefully monitored. This will permit fuel composition optimisation to improve fuel compatibility and it will help reducing ASTM international certification costs.

³⁴ Jetscreen project will be completed end of 2020 ; information is available on www.jetscreen-h2020.eu

4 Regulation Technical Issues

4.1 Status on CO₂ standard and market based measures

4.1.1 General status

The CAEP CO₂ Aircraft Standard

A first CO₂ international standard for aviation was delivered beginning of 2016 by CAEP 10th meeting (Committee of Aviation Environmental Protection) and approved consecutively by ICAO General Assembly in autumn 2016. It concerns all turbofan/turbojet aircrafts with an MTOM above 5700kg and turboprop aircrafts with an MTOM above 8618kg. It will apply to aircraft designs, for which application to Type Certification is received by the Airworthiness Authorities at or after 1st January 2020. Also, a regulatory production cut-off will apply to in-production aircraft after 1st January 2028 if they do not pass a less stringent “In-production” level.

A certification standard is constituted of a metric system, an associated certification procedure, and a regulatory level. The first important step in the elaboration of this new international standard was the definition of the metric system (see figure 40) and the certification procedure. This was achieved in 2013 at the CAEP 9th meeting, with acceptance of all ICAO contracting states including European states and further publication as an ICAO Circular 337. This metric is publicly available³⁵.

Figure 40: Agreed CO₂ standard metric system

³⁵ <http://www.icao.int/Meetings/Green/Documents/day%201pdf/session%203/3-Dickson.pdf>

The stringency levels (see figure 41) for New Type and In Production aircraft were defined during the following CAEP cycle (2013-2016). On 3 March 2017, the CO₂ Standard was adopted by the Council as a new Volume to Annex 16 (Volume III). It was agreed also in 2017, that this standard will be accompanied by a public database containing the metric value together with the MTOM of all in-production aircraft³⁶.

Figure 41: Agreed CO₂ standard regulatory levels

Important Statements (on CO₂ standard):

- The standard is one part of ICAO’s basket of measures to reduce CO₂ emissions from aviation.
- It is a **technology** standard, not an operational standard.
- The purpose of the ICAO-CAEP CO₂ standard is to continue to support advances in fuel efficient technology, and to provide regulatory pressure in addition to the existing & obvious market/economic benefits to be derived from reducing fuel consumption.
- The CO₂ emissions standard is a regulatory certification standard set at the **aeroplane** system level.

Market-Based Measures

Market-based measures (MBMs) may be considered as a complementary incentive, in addition to the CO₂ standard, to reduce CO₂ emissions. FORUM-AE had limited activity linked to this very political subject, however a fruitful workshop was organised, involving many European experts strongly involved in the ICAO discussions dedicated to this subject.

To keep historical track, we present hereafter, the project’s views beginning of year 2015. Since, then important progress has been achieved and the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for international Aviation (CORSIA) (agreed in October 2016 by ICAO 26th Assembly) was planned for introduction in 2020. More details on CORSIA together with an analysis of its implementation in

³⁶ As the standard is mandatory only for new aircraft for which a type certificate was requested after 1/01/2020, no public data is foreseen in the short term. However, the structure and procedures for submitting data to the ICAO CO₂ Certification Database have been agreed at CAEP and the database will be hosted and maintained by the USFAA

Europe, where an EU Emissions Trading Scheme is already in place, is provided in Appendix 4, written by DLR specialists.

2015 status and FORUM-AE vision on MBM:

- The proposed global MBM (GMBM) is part of the ICAO Basket of Measures and should complement other CO₂ reduction activities.
- The objective of the GMBM is to attain CNG2020³⁷.
- It's recognised that a lot of technical work has been completed but there remains a lot of work to complete the definition of the first global aviation market based measure.
- In order to address SCRC (Special Circumstances and Respective Capabilities) concerns:
 - Differentiation by Route (based on State to State) is currently under consideration but designing the details to satisfy all parties is complex and challenging.
 - There is general agreement that any differentiation should limit market distortion. Route based approach is a promising solution and analysis of this approach should be prioritised.
 - Phase-in of developing States is possible.
 - However, all Operators should participate with a minimum of MRV from the start even if they are going to be exempt.
- Robust yet simple Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV) is needed.
- Consideration of simplified procedures for small operators should be made
- The GMBM must have high environmental integrity including no double counting of emissions units.
- Need to identify the legal instruments and start planning the legislative process preferably as soon as possible
 - Europe should raise the need for a legal framework for the GMBM with the appropriate legal body of ICAO.
 - Requires agreement on Governance of the scheme.
 - Implementation and Regulation will need to be done at National/Regional level.
- Timescales are challenging:
 - According to the "Strawman" outline, ICAO has to implement MRV from the beginning of January 2018, with the overall global scheme commencing in 2020.
 - Progress in UNFCCC on Differentiated Responsibilities is important at COP21 in December 2015 in Paris to aid progress in ICAO. UNFCCC decisions about future carbon mechanisms may influence the availability of emissions units for aviation.

³⁷ Carbon Neutral Growth starting from 2020

- Europe will continue to help ICAO deliver what it promised.
- Europe needs to maintain modelling capability in this area, and work together to best use the available resources.
- The preference is for a global offsetting scheme.
- Some elements of the GMBM scheme do not necessarily need to be fully defined by the ICAO Assembly in 2016. For example, sustainable alternative fuel should be included in the GMBM in order to send a positive message to fuel producers but the design of the scheme should not be held up by the alternative fuel discussion.

Therefore a timeline of activities to be performed from now up until 2020 should be developed by ICAO.

4.1.2 Recommendations and needs

- 1) The CO₂ standard is now well established and further European activity should be to support the CAEP technology goal setting process and its association to the standard-setting process³⁸.

4.2 Status on NO_x and particles standards

4.2.1 General status

A first particles international standard for aviation was delivered beginning of 2016 at CAEP 10th meeting with an application date of 1st January 2020 for all in-production engines with a take-off thrust above 26.7kN. This first standard is more a “transition standard” ; it addresses non volatile Particulate Matters (nvPM) and is looking at the nvPM mass concentration at the engine exit. The aims of the CAEP10 standard were firstly to establish and validate a measurement protocol and secondly to provide an alternative to the old smoke number standard, considering some correlation between the nvPM mass concentration and the smoke number.

³⁸ The CAEP technology review took place as planned in 2017 to 2019, and the results of this review are detailed in the ICAO Doc 10127 - Independent Expert Integrated Technology Goals Assessment and Review for Engines and Aircraft. This was the first time that ICAO developed technology goals for noise, local air quality and CO₂ emissions in an integrated manner, with full consideration of the interdependencies between the technologies.

Figure 42: nvPM standard measurement system

A second one, more relevant to air quality and climate concern was therefore developed consecutively to be delivered at CAEP 11th meeting, beginning of 2019. It is based on nvPM total mass or number emitted during LTO (Landing and Take-Off) cycle, with a DP/F00 metric (DP = total mass or number over the LTO cycle ; F00 = Take-Off thrust) similarly to the NO_x standard.

Figure 43: DP/F00 type emissions standards

European stakeholders were very active in the standard development process, in particular thanks to European funded projects ([28]) and national projects ([29], [30]). The FORUM-AE workshops which were focused on nvPM standard, permitted important exchanges and dissemination among European stakeholders, and more detailed information and historical views from the project may be found in the associated proceedings.

Some of the key technical issues, which were addressed in order to be able to provide a robust standard at the CAEP 11th meeting in 2019, are the following:

- Fuel composition sensitivity (see figure 44 which illustrates sensitivity to fuel Hydrogen to Carbon ratio, H/C)
- Ambient conditions corrections
- Measurement uncertainties
- Particles losses (see figure 45 showing more important losses for smaller particles)
- Statistical correction (to represent the possible scattering between different engines of the same model)

Lastly, the main remaining and challenging task in 2017 was the definition of the DP/F00 mass and number limits as functions of F00 and FORUM-AE partners provided active support³⁹.

Figure 44 : Fuel composition effect on particles formation
 (EI = Emission Index = number of particles per kg fuel; H=hydrogen content)[30]

Figure 45: Particles loss mechanisms (RR input)

Concerning NO_x, the last increase of stringency was decided in 2010 (at CAEP 8th meeting) with application in 2014. The following table provides an historical summary of emissions standards. These standards are naturally incentives justifying the development of environmentally friendly aircraft/engine solutions.

³⁹ This second nvPM standard, expressed in terms of DP/F00 both in mass and number, versus engine F00, was duly delivered in 2019, with a regulatory limit for new certified engines after 1st January 2023, and a soft regulatory limit for in production engines after 1st January 2023.

Standard	CAEP meeting date	NOx			Smoke / Particles	Standard CO / UHC	CO2 Standard (aircraft level)
		Applicability date to new certified engines	Stringency increase (evaluated at OPR=30, F00=89kN)	Production cut-off?			
CAEP12	2022	na	Unchanged	discussed	Review of nvPM Regulatory Levels ; SN replaced by nvPM standard n°1	Unchanged	Unchanged
CAEP11	2019	na	Unchanged	No	2nd nvPM std expressed in DP/F00=f(F00) both for mass & number ; Applicability > 2023	Unchanged	Unchanged
CAEP10	2016	na	Unchanged	No	1st international standard on fines particles (~SN) applicability on 1/01/2020	Unchanged	1st international std on CO2 ; applicability: NT > 2020 & InP >2028
CAEP8	2010	janv-14	-15% from CAEP6	No	Unchanged	Unchanged	
CAEP6	2004	janv-08	-12% from CAEP4	Yes: 01/01/2013	Unchanged	Unchanged	
CAEP4	1998	janv-04	-16% from CAEP2	No	Unchanged	Unchanged	
CAEP2	1991	janv-96	-20% from CAEE	Yes: 01/01/2000	Smoke Number	Constant limit	
CAEP1	1981						

Table 11: historical overview of ICAO CAEP emissions standards

4.2.2 Recommendations and needs

- 1) Concerning NOx regulation, as there exists a well-established standard for which the last stringency was agreed in 2010 for application in 2014, appropriate monitoring work is justified.
- 2) Further work is required to support the future nvPM standard, in particular to populate an aero-engine nvPM database for in-production engines (turbofans>26.7KN, turbofans<26.7KN, turboprops, turboshafts, and APUs), and to provide the information needed for a certification requirement (fuel specifications, corrections, and analysis procedures etc.)⁴⁰.
- 3) Research organisations and engine manufacturers need to work together with airports to help update their PM models, and to help them find good measurement techniques to identify different PM sources at the airport.
- 4) Work is required to update the state of science on aircrafts nvPM emissions against emissions from other sources and in comparison to volatile PM. Scientists want to know about nvPM with and without volatile coating and morphology and size, and have many other science questions beyond simply mass and number.

⁴⁰ This recommendation was done in 2017 and was relevant at this time. Now the 2nd standard is delivered and publication before end 2020 of an up-dated edb containing nvPM certification data is planned ; so this recommendation is outdated for turbofans>26.7kN but still valid for engines in other categories

5 New assessment of progress towards ACARE Goals

Based on results synthesized in previous chapters, and following the mid-term provisional assessment delivered in 2015, a new assessment on the progress towards ACARE environmental goals linked to aircraft emissions could be established, and reflects the status end of 2017. This final assessment, follows the ones done by OPTI and AGAPE projects respectively in 2012 and 2010.

FORUM-AE 2017 assessment:

- Qualitative Goal: *“Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in formulating a prioritised environmental action plan and establishes global environmental standards.”*

Progress has been achieved in scientific understanding of aviation impact on climate. Key recommendations are proposed however by FORUM-AE, to progress further, and in particular: the question of relevant climate metric is raised, idea of Climate Change Function (CCF) is promoted, need to better quantify the effect of non volatile particles on contrails properties is highlighted. Sticking to Radiative Forcing (RF), a new figure since Lee et al one (in 2009), is proposed by DLR.

- Quantitative Goals on CO₂ & NO_x:

The progress achieved today, both in maturity and in reduction of CO₂ or NO_x is the fruit of a large variety of projects (Clean Sky, LEMCOTEC/ENOVAL/E-BREAK, high number of smaller projects). The NO_x LTO assessment assumes a follow-up of LEMCOTEC combined with further activities in Clean Sky, which would be necessary to achieve TRL6 for the various engine categories. Cruise NO_x status should be considered with some care; it is based on Clean Sky Technology Evaluator for SMR aircraft category. The status is summarised in the following table:

	Reference 2000	ACARE 2020 Goals (at TRL6)		ACARE 2050 Goals (at TRL6)		FORUM-AE Assessment (2017) (extrapolated at TRL 5-6 in 2020)
		High Level	detailed (SRA)	High Level	detailed (SRIA)	
CO ₂	<i>Representative technology of aircraft & engine with 2000 EIS, & representative 2000 ATM</i>	"-50% per pass km"	aircraft: -20% to -25% engine: -15% to -20% ATM: -5% to -10%	"-75% per pass km"	aircraft & engine: -68% ATM: -12% Other: -12%	aircraft + engine +ATM: ≈ -27% Regional ≈ [-38%, -41%] SMR ≈ [-19%, -26%] LR in average per pass km
NO _x (LTO)		"-80%"	engine: -60% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	"-90%"	engine: -75% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	engine: [-60%, -70%] CAEP6
NO _x (Cruise)		"-80%"	Achieved through -50% Fuel Burn & -60% cruise EINO _x reduction	"-90%"	Achieved through -75% Fuel Burn & further cruise EINO _x reduction	~ -40% (with high uncertainty) in average per pass km
Other emissions		"damaging emissions reduced"	emissions qualitatively reduced (particles, CO, UHC) and better understanding of impacts	"emissions-free taxiing" + qualitative reduction	knowledge of emissions (particles, VOC) and better understanding of impacts	experience gained in nvPM measurement campaigns on Engines & better knowledge of engines particles emissions

Table 12: FORUM-AE 2017 assessment of progress towards ACARE 2020 & 2050 goals

From this assessment, we try to estimate which percentage of the final goal is already achieved (at TRL6), is expected with on-going projects (at TRL6), or is not yet covered (remaining gap to achieve the goal at TRL6), in the same way it was done in OPTI. This exercise is very delicate because it mixes an estimation both in terms of expected reduction and in terms of maturity and it oversimplifies the situation (the status may differ from one engine category to another one, from one manufacturer to another one). Nevertheless, considering all the necessary reserve, the current situation is summarised in the following picture; since OPTI 2012 assessment, we consider some progress on CO₂, and a small one on NO_x mainly in terms of maturation.

Fig. 46: FORUM-AE 2017 simplified assessment of progress towards ACARE 2020 goal
(with “abusive” simplification)

From this assessment the main message is the following: ACARE 2020 CO₂ goal is not met, knowing most of the demonstrated reduction today comes from the propulsion system. ACARE 2020 NO_x goal is achievable for LTO NO_x but requires still maturation although one European manufacturer, is very close to TRL6; further progress is needed especially for smaller engines. Only approximate status is given on cruise NO_x: there is still important uncertainty on cruise NO_x for lean combustion technology, and trend for higher compression ratio to improve fuel efficiency balances possible improvement from combustion technology. Lastly, further work to progress towards ACARE 2050 NO_x goal (both at LTO and cruise levels) should be accomplished with simultaneous non volatile particles reduction.

- Quantitative Goal: **“Aircraft movements are emission-free when taxiing”**

This goal may rely on electric taxiing (with fully green electricity) but no review of potential solutions was carried up inside the project.

- Qualitative Goal: **“Europe is established as a center of excellence on sustainable alternative fuels, including those for aviation, based on a strong European energy policy.”**

One can distinguish between up-stream side (production) and down-stream side (engine compatibility) projects. ITAKA was the main up-stream project, and was completed in 2016.

It permitted to gain concrete experience in producing drop-in fuel from Camelina. Concerning down-stream projects, JETSCREEN project was initiated beginning of 2017 and meets well the investigation needs expressed after the sustainable aviation fuel forum (SAFF) organised jointly by FORUM-AE and ITAKA in 2014. However, despite this RTD effort, perspective of renewable alternative fuel production remains quite modest. Alternative fuel topic has also open some interest in fuel composition optimisation in general. To have more complete status on alternative fuel one should also refer to CORE-JetFuel coordination action entirely dedicated to the subject and completed in 2016.

6 Up-dated status mid-2020

Further iterations inside the FORUM-AE consortium confirm that mid-2020, most of the 2017 status and recommendations are still valid (message expressed in [32]). We stress in particular the following points:

- ❖ Vision 2020 NO_x goal is effectively met (at least by RR who achieved TRL6), but Vision 2020 CO₂ goal is not met. nvPM remains a new challenge (Air Quality + contrails indirect effect on climate)
- ❖ During the 2 years (2018 & 2019), the progress was mostly on technology maturation which was actively pursued
- ❖ A tremendous technological effort is mandatory to mature most promising solutions in order to reduce aggressively CO₂ (and to meet Vision 2020 goal and progress towards Flightpass 2050 goal)
- ❖ A significant effort is still necessary to deliver low NO_x, low nvPM technology for all aircraft engine applications, and satisfying all operability constraints. Possible trend with higher OPR & T41 engines makes it even more challenging
- ❖ Alternative Energy Carriers solutions (LH₂, LCH₄, HEP, FEP...): still at low TRL, with many technical uncertainties (aircraft, engine levels) as well as environmental benefits uncertainties (LCA CO₂ budget, H₂O effect)

7 Conclusions

FORUM-AE coordination action was the frame of intense technical exchanges during 5 years (from 2013 to 2017) on a large number of major topics linked to aircraft emissions and their environmental impacts. Key conclusions are synthesised in this document in each of the 3 chapters (2, 3, 4) addressing respectively environmental impacts, mitigation solutions, and regulation technical issues. The work based on topical workshops and European RTD monitoring, supported a new assessment of the progress towards ACARE goals (summarised in chapter 5). A simple up-dated mid-2020 status is provided in Chapter 6 completed by various added footnotes in order to stress new relevant results and publications, which were produced in the meantime. FORUM-AE provided also the technical expertise to ACARE working group on Environment and Energy.

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Appendix 1) General information on FORUM-AE

A.1.1 Consortium

The consortium was constituted of 13 partners, and 3 associated partners.

Partners	Participant Organisation Name	Short name	Country
1 (CO)	Snecma	SN	FR
2	Airbus SAS	AI	FR
3	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft und Raumfahrt e.V.	DLR	DE
4	Deutsche Lufthansa AG	DLH	DE
5	ECATS	ECATS	BE
6	Flughafen Zurich AG	FZAG	CH
7	IFP Energies nouvelles	IFPEN	FR
8	Manchester Metropolitan University	MMU	UK
9	Stichting Nationaal Lucht - En Ruimtevaart laboratorium	NLR	NL
10	Office National d'Etudes et de Recherches Aérospatiales	ON	FR
11	Rolls Royce Group plc	RR	UK
12	Rolls Royce Deutschland Ltd & Co KG	RRD	DE
13	SENASA	SENASA	ES
14	Eurocontrol (<i>associated</i>)	ECTL	FR
15	Joint Research Center (<i>associated</i>)	JRC	BE
16	Turbomeca (<i>associated</i>)	TM	FR

A.1.2 Project's organisation

The project's organisation was the following:

EC Scientific Officer:

2015-2017: Christiane Bruynooghe (DG Research & Innovation)
 2013-2014: Marco Brusati (DG Research & Innovation)

A1.3 Organisational scheme of a new European Network on aviation environmental issues

A potential follow-up of FORUM-AE was envisaged by the consortium with an enlarged scope, and the following organisation, in order to address at European level all environmental issues linked to future air transportation.

Appendix 2) Monitored projects

The main RTD programs relevant to FORUM-AE scope are provided in the following table but this is not fully exhaustive. Also, some important national projects were considered.

PROJECT	T0	Coordinator	TITLE	TYPE
REACT4C	2010	DLR*	Reducing Emissions from Aviation by Changing Trajectories for the Benefit of Climate	Impacts
ECATS	2005	ECATS*	Environmental Compatible Air Transport System => Foundation	Impacts
IAGOS	2008	RC Jülich	In service Aircraft for a Global Observing System	Impacts
IAGOS ERI	2009	RC Jülich	In service Aircraft for a Global Observing System / European Research Infrastructure	Impacts
CARIBIC	2004	MPI Chemie, Mainz	Civil aircraft for the regular investigation of the atmosphere based on an instrument container	Impacts
QUANTIFY	2005	DLR*	Quantifying the Climate Impact of Global and European Transport Systems	Impacts
CleanSky - SFWA	2008	AI*	SMART Fixed Wing Aircraft	Aircraft
CleanSky - GRA	2008	Alenia	The Green Regional Aircraft	Aircraft
CleanSky - GRC	2008	Eurocopter	Green Rotorcraft	Aircraft
CleanSky2	2014	Airbus, Dassault	Clean-Sky 1 Follow-up with: * Large Passenger Aircraft platform (LPA) * Regional Aircraft platform (RA) * Fast Rotorcraft platform (FRC)	Aircraft
NACRE	2005	AI*	New Aircraft Concepts Research	Aircraft
AHEAD	2011	TU Delft	Advanced Hybrid Engines for Aircraft Development	Aircraft
DISPURSAL	2013	Bauhaus	Distributed Propulsion and Ultra-high By-pass Rotor Study at Aircraft Level	Aircraft
CleanSky - SAGE	2008	RR*&SN*	Sustainable And Green Engine	Engine
CleanSky2	2014	Safran Aircraft Engines, RR...	Clean-Sky 1 Follow-up with: * Aircraft, Engines, Systems ITDs (Integrated Technology Developments)	Engines
DREAM	2008	RR*	validation of Radical Engine Architecture systems	Engine & Fuel
NEWAC	2006	MTU	NEW Aero engine Core concepts	Engine HP
VITAL	2005	SN*	Environmentally Friendly Aero-Engine	Engine BP
LEMCO TEC	2011	RRD*	Low Emissions Core-Engine Technologies	Engine HP
EBREAK	2012	TM*	Engine Breakthrough components and subsystems	Engine
ENOVAL	2013	MTU	The Engine mOdule Validators	Engine BP
ULTIMATE	2015	Chalmers	Ultra Low emission Technology Innovations for Mid-century Aircraft Turbine Engines	Engine
SOPRANO	2016	Safran-Tech	Soot Processes and Radiation in Aeronautical inNOvative combustors	Combustor
KIAI	2009	SN*	Knowledge for Ignition, Acoustics and Instabilities	Combustor
FIRST	2010	RR*	Fuel injection research	Combustor
FACTOR	2010	SN*	Turbine combustor interaction	Combustor
IMPACT-AE	2011	RRD*	Design methodologies	Combustor
TECC-AE	2008	SN*	Technology Enhancements for Clean Combustion	Combustor
INTELLECT D.M.	2003	RRD*	Integrated Lean Low-Emission Combustor Design Methodology	Combustor
TIMCOP-AE	2006	TM*	Toward Innovative Methods for Combustion Prediction in Aero-engines	Combustor
TLC	2005	SN*	Towards Lean Combustion	Combustor
LOPOCOTEP	2000	SN*	Low POUllutant COmbustor TEchnology Project	Combustor
SESAR 1	2007	JU	Single European Sky ATM Research	Operations
SESAR/IMET	2011	NLR	Investigating the optimal approach for future trajectory prediction systems to use METeorological uncertainty information	Operations
SESAR 2020	2014	JU	SESAR 1 follow-up	Operations
SESAR/ATM4E	2015	DLR*	Air Traffic Management for Environment	Operations
CleanSky - SGO	2008	Thales	System for Green Operation	Operations
AIRE	2009	SJU-FAA	Atlantic Interoperability Initiative to Reduce Emissions	Operations
RECREATE	2007	NLR	REsearch on a CRuiser – Enabled Air Transport Environment	Operations
ERAT	2007	To70	Environmental Responsible Air Transport	Operations
CS-EcoDesign	2008	DA&FHF	Eco-Design (co-led by Dassault & Fraunhofer)	Recyclability
ALFA-BIRD	2008	Eu-Vri	Alternative Fuels and Biofuels for Aircraft Development	Fuel
JETSCREEN	2017	DLR*	JET Fuel SCREENing and Optimization	Fuel
SWAFEA	2009	Onera	Sustainable Way for Alternative Fuels and Energy in Aviation	Fuel
burnFAIR	2010	LH*	Searching for a viable kerosene replacement	Fuel
BIOREFLY	2015	Biochemtex	Industrial scale demonstration biorefinery on lignin-based aviation fuel	Fuel
SUN-to-LIQUID	2016	Bauhaus Luftfahrt	SUNlight-to-LIQUID: Integrated solar-thermochemical synthesis of liquid hydrocarbon fuels	Fuel
BIOTFuel	2017	Total	BioTFuel: Developing Second-Generation Biofuels	Fuel
BFSJ	2015	Swedish Biofuels AB	Production of fully synthetic paraffinic jet fuel from wood and other biomass	Fuel
Photofuel	2015	Volkswagen AG	Biocatalytic solar fuels for sustainable mobility in Europe	Fuel
ITAKA	2012	SEN*	Initiative Towards sustainable Kerosene for Aviation	Fuel
GreenAir	2009	EADS	Generation of Hydrogen by Kerosene Reforming via Efficient and Low-Emission New Alternative, Innovative, Refined Technologies for Aircraft	Fuel (Other type)

Appendix 3) ACARE goals

ACARE Environmental Goals by 2050

- ❖ CO2 emissions per passenger kilometre have been reduced by 75%, NOx emissions by 90% and perceived noise by 65%, all relative to the year 2000.
- ❖ Aircraft movements are emission-free when taxiing.
- ❖ Air vehicles are designed and manufactured to be recyclable.
- ❖ Europe is established as a centre of excellence on sustainable alternative fuels, including those for aviation, based on a strong European energy policy.
- ❖ Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in formulating a prioritised environmental action plan and establishes global environmental standards.

“ACARE environmental goals (Flightpath 2050 – see [2])”

Combustion Technology Development

“Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) for combustion technology”

Appendix 4) EU ETS / CORSIA analysis by DLR

How to proceed with the EU ETS for aviation in the period 2017-2020 in light of the forthcoming global market-based measure CORSIA?⁴¹

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Abstract

The air transport sector contributes to climate change by emitting substantial amounts of CO₂ and other climate relevant species. To address this problem, two important CO₂ trading schemes for aviation are in force, resp. will be in force in the future: The EU Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS) for aviation which was introduced in 2012 and CORSIA (Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation) which has been agreed on the level of the International Civil Aviation Organization ICAO in October 2016. The authors analyze and compare both reduction schemes from an environmental as well as economic point of view. Furthermore, based on environmental as well as economic modelling results, alternative geographical design options for the European Trading Scheme are investigated for the interim period until 2020.

1. Background

The air transport sector contributes to climate change by emitting substantial amounts of carbon dioxide (CO₂). To limit these emissions, two important CO₂ trading schemes for aviation are in force, respectively will be in force in the near future: The EU Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS) for aviation and CORSIA (Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation) which has been agreed on the level of the International Civil Aviation Organization ICAO recently.

In 2012, international aviation became part of the EU ETS (Council of the European Union, 2009a and 2009b). Until (at least) 2020, all flights starting from or landing at European airports are subject to the EU ETS, apart from a few exemptions. In light of strong international opposition against the EU ETS for aviation and ongoing negotiations on ICAO level, the EU decided to limit the coverage of the EU ETS to emissions from all flights within the European Economic Area (EEA) for the period 2013 to 2016 (so-called “Stop-the-Clock” regulation; Commission of the European Union, 2012).

In October 2016, CORSIA has been agreed on at the 39th ICAO Assembly after decades of difficult international negotiations (ICAO, 2016). CORSIA will be in force from 2020 onwards with an increasing number of participating states over time.

In light of Assembly Resolution A39-3, the EU will have to decide how to continue with the EU ETS for aviation in the years to come. This is because the so-called “Stop-the-Clock” legislation was limited until the end of 2016 with clear reference to the outcome of the ICAO Assembly. Apart from temporarily extending the Stop-the-Clock regime, a possible approach for adjusting the EU ETS would be to amend its geographical scope.

⁴¹ This analysis was provided by DLR in 2017, and reflects the situation at this time.

The aim of this paper is to discuss different options for the EU concerning the inclusion of aviation within the EU ETS framework until CORSIA starts as well as their economic and environmental consequences. This paper is organized as follows: In section 2, some basic facts, the legal background and the current situation of the EU ETS are presented. The new CORSIA scheme will then be explained in detail in the third section. Alternative options for geographical scope of the EU ETS as well as their environmental and economic impacts are discussed in section 4 of this paper.

2. EU ETS for aviation: Basic facts, legal backgrounds and current situation

Legal framework for the EU ETS for aviation are the EU Directives 2008/101/EC and 2009/29 EC (Council of the European Union, 2009a, 2009b). According to this legislation, European and third-country aircraft operators are responsible for holding and surrendering allowances for CO₂ emissions for most flights to, from an within Europe. For compliance, EU Allowances (EUAs) as well as permits from the Kyoto-based “Clean Development Mechanism” (CERs) and “Joint Implementation” (ERUs) are accepted.

From 2013 until 2020, the total quantity of allowances allocated to aircraft operators will be limited to 95 per cent of the average historical aviation emissions of the years 2004-2006 (so-called overall “cap”). Allowances allocated to aircraft operators are valid within the aviation sector only, but aircraft operators are free to purchase additional permits from other markets. In the period 2013 - 2020, aircraft operators may use emission permits from “Joint Implementation” and “Clean Development Mechanism” for up to 1.5 per cent of the number of allowances individually required for surrendering in a given year. This figure was a political compromise agreed upon after long and controversial negotiations (Scheelhaase et al., 2012). According to EU Directive 2009/29 EC, flights from third countries which have introduced ‘equivalent’ CO₂ reducing measures, can be excluded from the EU ETS. It will be up to the European Commission to decide whether a third country measure is equivalent (Council of the European Union, 2009b). In practice, due to the lack of equivalent measures in countries of relevance, this option does not (yet) play a role.

Some exemptions from the EU ETS are granted. Inter alia, flights performed within the framework of public service obligations (PSO) on routes within outermost regions or on PSO (public service obligation) routes with an annual capacity of fewer than 30,000 seats are excluded. Another exemption refers to flights performed by commercial air transport operators operating either fewer than 243 flights per four-month period for three consecutive four-month periods (so-called ‘de minimis’ clause) or operators with total CO₂-emissions of less than 10,000 tonnes per year. The rationale behind the ‘de minimis’ clause was to reduce the administrative costs for operators with a low number of flights to and from Europe (Scheelhaase et al., 2012).

In 2013, the Council of the EU and the EU Parliament agreed to temporarily limit the coverage of the EU ETS to flights within the European Economic Area (EEA) only - which covers the EU Member States, Norway and Iceland. This so-called “Stop-the-Clock” regulation was limited to the period 2013 to 2016. Formally, the original scope of the EU ETS for aviation as introduced in 2012 would be in force again from 2017 onwards. Whether this will be the case or not remains to be seen.

3. CORSIA (Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation): Background, basic principles, timeline, open questions and challenges

Since 1997, ICAO had been working on possible policy measures for the limitation or reduction of international aviation’s greenhouse gas emissions. As it is the case with many UN agencies, negotiations turned out to be difficult and progress was slow. Milestones were the Assembly Resolutions A37 (ICAO, 2010), A38 (ICAO, 2013) and A39 (ICAO, 2016), agreed upon in 2010, 2013 and 2016, respectively.

At the 37th ICAO Assembly (Assembly Resolution A37-19), the goal of carbon neutral growth from the year 2020 onwards – the “CNG 2020 goal” had been agreed. The rationale behind this goal is to reduce the environmental footprint stemming from aviation’s GHG emissions. At the 38th Assembly, this goal was reaffirmed and the development of a global market-based measure (GMBM) scheme for international aviation for decision by the 39th ICAO Assembly was agreed (ICAO, 2013).

The need for a GMBM scheme was recognized because the implementation of technical and operational measures as well as an – assumed - increased switch to biofuels alone are considered unlikely to ensure achieving the CNG 2020 goal (Figure 1). Hence, economic or – so-called – (global) market-based measures are needed to close the remaining gap between 2020 and 2035 or beyond.

Air Transport Emissions Reduction Roadmap (Source: IATA, available online)

By agreeing on Resolution A39-3, the 39th ICAO Assembly has decided for a formalized GMBM system in form of an offset scheme called CORSIA. In principle, in a CO₂ offset scheme, carbon credits are used for compliance. A carbon credit represents the avoidance of a certain amount of carbon dioxide equivalent (CO_{2e}). Carbon credits can be derived by greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction projects that deliver measurable reductions in emissions.

CORSIA aims at supporting the CNG goal from 2020 onwards. Resolution A39-3 provides the calculation method for the number of offsets airlines have to purchase in order to compensate for additional emissions stemming from the sector’s post-2020 growth.

In the following, we briefly present the scheme’s main characteristics and discuss some major issues, also in light of the (current) application of the EU ETS to the air transport sector in Europe. Figure 2 provides a brief overview of CORSIA’s key elements.

**) Except Least Developed Countries (LDCs), Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and Landlocked Developing Countries (LLDCs) unless they volunteer to participate.*

Timeline and functioning of CORSIA (Source: Own figure on the basis of ICAO, 2016)

According to Resolution A39-3, CORSIA’s main principles and functioning can be summarized as follows (see also Figure 2):

- (a) CORSIA is an offset scheme, i.e. emissions of the air transport sector are to be offset – at the carrier level – by purchasing carbon credits or by investments in projects that help reducing CO₂ or GHG emissions in other sectors. Due to technical boundaries, in some sectors emission reductions can be achieved cheaper and hence more efficiently than in others. On a global level, different carbon offset markets and quality assurance standards for carbon offsetting exist, see for instance Gold Standard, 2017.
- (b) CORSIA starts from 2020 and consists of three phases: a Pilot Phase (from 2021-2023), Phase 1 (2024-2026), and Phase 2 (2027-2035).
- (c) Offset requirements are defined by the routes flown. Only routes between participating states (“CORSIA States”) are subject to these requirements. We refer to these routes as “CORSIA routes” and to emissions stemming from these routes as “CORSIA emissions”. CORSIA requirements will change within its three phases:

- In the pilot phase and in phase 1 (until 2026), participation in the scheme is voluntary. As of February 2017, 66 states are expected to join the scheme on a voluntary basis, which are expected to represent 86.5 % of global RTKs. (ICAO, 2017).
 - In Phase 2, CORSIA will become mandatory for all ICAO Contracting States whose carrier (based on AOC issuance) “have an individual share of international aviation activities in RTKs in year 2018 above 0.5 per cent of total RTKs or whose cumulative share in the list of States from the highest to the lowest amount of RTKs reaches 90 per cent of total RTKs, except Least Developed Countries (LDCs), Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and Landlocked Developing Countries (LLDCs) unless they volunteer to participate in this phase” (ICAO, 2016).
 - Aircraft operators offsetting requirements can be reduced through the use of sustainable alternative fuels.
- (d) In an attempt to minimize market distortion, the Assembly has ruled that all aircraft operators have to surrender offsets for emissions stemming from CORSIA routes, irrespectively of their home country, except for
- a. small emitters (airlines with less than 10,000 tons CO₂ p.a.);
 - b. flights with aircraft between 5.7 tons Maximum Take-Off Mass (MTOM);
 - c. humanitarian/medical and firefighting operations; and
 - d. – for a period of up to three years each – ‘new entrants’, as long as they do not represent more than 0.1% of total RTK.
- (e) The amount of CO₂ emissions which individual airlines have to offset depends on two factors: Firstly, the carrier’s individual emissions on CORSIA-routes and secondly the growth of the aviation sector. In the later years, the carrier’s individual growth rates are considered to an increasing extent:
- a. In the Pilot Phase and Phase 1, carriers serving CORSIA-routes have to offset their individual CORSIA-emissions in the given year multiplied by the sectors growth factor. The latter refers to the growth between the baseline year (mean of 2019 and 2020 emissions) and the given year, i.e.:

Emissions to be offset by Carrier x in year t = [CORSIA-emissions_{t,x} * Sector growth_{baseline-given year t}]

The aviation sector growth between the given and the baseline year is defined as [(CORSIA-emissions_{given_year t} – CORSIA-emissions_{baseline}) / (CORSIA-emissions_{given_year t})]

Within the voluntary Pilot Phase, states are free to replace the given year t by the year 2020 as basis for their carriers’ offsetting requirements.

- b. Within Phase 2, the growth factor to be applied to a carrier’s CORSIA-emissions will – with an increasing percentage – consider each carrier’s individual growth, i.e.:

Emissions to be offset by Carrier x in year t = [CORSIA-emissions_{t,x} * (s * Sector growth_{baseline-given year t} + i * Individual growth_{x, baseline-given year t})]

with
s = 100% and i = 0% between 2027 and 2029,
s = at most 80% and i = at least 20% between 2030 and 2032, and
s = at most 30% and i = at least 70% between 2033 and 2035;
with the ICAO Council recommending the percentage of ‘i’, in 2028 to the
Assembly.

Which are the main differences between CORSIA and the EU ETS for aviation? Key differences of the schemes are:

- Due to the principal design differences of the schemes (offset versus cap-and-trade), the method of setting the emissions cap is different. The same applies to the permit allocation method to the aircraft operators: While in CORSIA offsets can be initiated by the aircraft operators and/or purchased on the offset markets, in the EU ETS allowances are allocated to the aircraft operators by the European States, and can also be purchased on the permit markets.
- Environmental benefits: Although the CORSIA coverage of 90% looks quite huge at first sight, hence implying a massive environmental effectivity, actually only small parts of total emissions have to be offset, namely those emissions that stem from air traffic post-2020 growth. The EU-ETS, in contrast, requires airlines to surrender emissions allowances for all of their traffic under the EU-ETS regime, albeit a significant percentage of allowances is allocated free of charge.
- The CORSIA AOC criterion in some cases, leads to strange exemptions since routes to, from or between countries with high air traffic volumes but a lack of (in a worldwide context) significant home carriers may be excluded from the scheme. To our knowledge, this refers to countries like Egypt, Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Pakistan, Kenya, Mauritius, the Seychelles or the Maldives, some of which are even served by Emirates’ A380s. Although on these routes large amounts of CO₂ are emitted, they will not fall under CORSIA. In other words: a number of routes flown by major and potent carriers are – without real justification – left out of the scheme. This leads to a further reduction of the scheme’s environmental effectiveness.

4. Political options for the EU to adjust the EU ETS for aviation: Different options of geographical scope of the EU ETS and associated environmental and economic consequences

The Commission of the EU will have to adjust the EU ETS for aviation in light of ICAO’s decision in October 2016. From a European perspective, this is an area of conflict: On the one hand, the EU ETS for stationary sources in which the trading scheme for aviation is embedded is clearly designed to be in force until 2050. And the EU ETS for aviation as intended in 2008 aims at ambitious CO₂ reductions by international aviation. On the other hand, ICAO is the UN agency responsible for limiting or reducing greenhouse gas emissions from international aviation. This responsibility has been allocated to ICAO by the Annex I Parties of the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 (UNFCCC, 1997). But CORSIA won’t be starting on a voluntary basis until 2020 and on a mandatory basis until 2027.

Against this background, a possible approach for proceeding with the EU ETS for aviation is to extend the “Stop-the-Clock”-regime or to adjust its geographical scope, both at least until 2020. On behalf of the German Environmental Agency, DLR has investigated principal options of geographical scope of the EU ETS for aviation as well as their economic and environmental effects, see Grimme et al., 2015 and Scheelhaase et al., 2016 for details. Main results of the study are presented in the following.

In total, seven options have been analyzed which differ by geographical scope and exceptions. As a reference, the impacts of the Full Scope (Option 1) and Reduced Scope (Option 7) approaches have been analyzed. While Option 1 assumes the continuance of the EU ETS for aviation as originally intended in 2008, Option 7 represents the geographical scope of the scheme as introduced by the EU according to the “Stop-the-Clock” regulation in 2014.

The core of the analysis was a geographical scope according to the 50:50 approach, in which half of the emissions of international aviation between EEA and third countries will be regulated by the EU-ETS (Option 2). Besides a pure 50:50 approach without any exceptions, we also discussed an option where emissions are capped at the border of a third country (Option 3). Furthermore, Option 4 assumed the exclusion of any emissions in international airspace from the EU-ETS. Two additional options based on airspace assumed that emissions of flights to/from airports outside the EEA are fully regulated by EU-ETS, as long as they are emitted in EEA airspace (Option 6) or in EEA and international airspace (Option 5), respectively. Underlying assumption of all options is that Great Britain will remain part of the EEA for the timeframe in question.

Likely geographical options are from today’s point of view:

- Option 1: (“Full Scope”, i. e. EU ETS as intended in 2008);
- Option 2: (“50:50 Scope”);
- Option 7 (“Reduced Scope”, i.e. extension of the Stop-the-Clock regime).

Which amounts of emissions would be covered by the EU ETS under these options? According to our modelling results (for full results please refer to Grimme et al., 2015 and Scheelhaase et al., 2016), the largest environmental impacts can be expected for an option assuming the originally intended scope of the EU ETS for aviation. Under this option all flights between the EU/EEA and third countries would be fully covered by the EU ETS. In this “Full Scope” option, about 315 million tons CO₂ would be subject to regulation in 2020. On the other end of the scale, the “Stop-the-clock” option 7 would only lead to about 80 million tons CO₂ regulated by the EU ETS in the same year. As a possible compromise, option 2 would represent almost 198 million tons CO₂.

Which environmental savings can be expected for these geographical options? According to EU-legislation, all CO₂ emissions exceeding the ‘cap’ have to be abated in the aviation sector or in other sectors regulated by emissions trading schemes. Our modelling results show that CO₂-reduction requirements for the airlines will cover a full range: While Option 1 leads to the reduction of about 105 million tons CO₂ in 2020, Option 2 induces savings of about 62 million tons and Option 7 of only about 20 million tons CO₂, in the same year.

The following table presents the estimated environmental impacts of Options 1, 2 and 7 for the timeframe 2006-2030 in detail.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 7	Option 1	Option 2	Option 7
Year	CO ₂ emissions under the EU-ETS, in m tons			CO ₂ emissions reduced, in m tons		
	Full Scope	50:50	Reduced Scope	Full Scope	50:50	Reduced Scope
2006	230.55	148.25	65.95	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
2010	242.05	154.88	67.70	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
2014	260.92	164.62	68.31	50.57	29.35	8.13
2017	287.01	180.45	73.89	76.66	45.19	13.72
2018	296.76	186.37	75.98	86.41	51.11	15.81
2019	306.88	192.51	78.13	96.53	57.24	17.96
2020	315.21	197.62	80.02	104.86	62.36	19.85
2030	411.04	256.15	101.25	200.69	120.89	41.08

Environmental impacts of different geographical options of the EU ETS for aviation.
Source: Own table on the basis of Grimme et al., 2015.

The associated economic impacts can be summarized as follows: In the “Full Scope” option, total costs for purchasing allowances have been estimated at 540 million € under the assumption of an allowance price of 5 €/t CO₂ and 1.08 billion € assuming an allowance price of 10 €/t CO₂, respectively, in the year 2017. Therefore, Option 1 would induce the highest costs for the airlines under the scheme. In contrast, Option 7 would lead to the lowest costs: Here, aircraft operators would have to spend about 113 million € (again assuming an allowance price of 5 €/t CO₂) and 227 million € (10 €/t CO₂) for purchasing the required allowances in the same year. If all flights within the EEA were fully covered by the EU ETS plus 50% of the emissions of international aviation between EEA and third countries (Option 2), total ETS costs at the airline level are estimated at 327 million € (5 €/t CO₂) and 655 million € (10 €/t CO₂), respectively.

Competitive impacts of the options analyzed are expected to be relatively small at today’s relatively low allowance prices. In January 2017, prices for European Allowances were at about 5 €/per ton CO₂, on average. But it should not be forgotten that any geographical option which includes some flights and excludes others will principally bear risks of diverting routes and/or passenger flows and therefore creates the potential for competitive distortions and carbon leakage. For instance, the one-stop connection Oslo-Athens-Beirut is to a great part regulated by the EU ETS, even under the “Stop-the-clock” regime. And the competing flight Oslo-Istanbul-Beirut is fully excluded because Turkey is not a part of the EEA.

On the other hand, any EU-ETS avoidance strategy by the airlines will also create additional costs:

- for fuel for serving longer flight distances,
- higher labor costs due to more stopovers and
- will lead to inferior marketing chances due to longer journey times.

According to our modelling results, at the current relatively low prices for allowances and fuel, incentives for avoiding reactions by the airlines under the EU ETS can be considered relatively small. But this will be subject to change if allowance prices will rise.

All in all, the EU has a number of options to adjust the current EU ETS for aviation until 2020 (and beyond). The associated environmental and economic impacts differ to a great extent, depending on the assumed geographical scope and exemptions. Against this background, a systematic in-depth analysis of all options from a European perspective is highly recommended.

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Appendix 5) Abbreviations

Acronym	Description
AAR	Air to Air Refueling
ACARE	Advisory Council for Aeronautical Research in Europe
AISBL	Association International sans but lucratif
AMAN	Arrival MANagement systems
APU	Auxiliary Power Unit
AQ	Air Quality
ATM	Air Traffic Management
BC	Black Carbon
BPR	By-Pass Ratio
BUW	Bergische Universität Wuppertal, Germany
CAEP	Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection, ICAO
CARS	Coherent Anti-Stokes Raman Spectroscopy
CCF	Climate Change Functions
CDM	Collaborative Decision Making
CMC	Ceramic Matrix Composite
CO	Carbon monoxide
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COC	Cash Operating Cost
COP21	21 st Conference of Parties (of UNFCCC)
CROR	Contra Rotating Open Rotor
DLH	Deutsche Lufthansa
DLR	German Aerospace Center
EC	European Commission
ECATS	ECATS International Association
ECN	Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands
ECS	Environmental Control System
ECTL	EUROCONTROL
EDB	ICAO's Aircraft Engine Emissions Databank
EEA	European Environment Agency
EGTS	Electric Green Taxiing System
EI, EIm, EIn	Emission Index, mass EI, number EI
ENVISA	French company ENVISA SAS

EPA	Environmental Protection Agency, US
ERF	Effective Radiative Forcing
EU	European Union
EUROCONTROL	European Organisation for the Safety of Air Navigation
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration, US
FB	Fuel Burn
FC	Fuel Cell
FEP	Full Electric Propulsion
FFM	Fuel Flow Method
FLOP	Fleet Optimisation
FOCA	Federal Office for Civil Aviation, CH
F00	Take-Off thrust
FORUM-AE	Forum on Aviation and Emissions, European FP7 Coordination Action project
FP7	7 th Frame-work Program in RTD (of the European Commission)
FPR	Fan Pressure Ratio
Fraport	Fraport AG, Frankfurt Airport Services Worldwide
FMS	Flight Management Systems
FRS	Filtered Rayleigh Scattering
FZAG	Flughafen Zürich AG
GMBM	Global Market Based Measures
GSE	ground support equipment
GTF	Geared Turbo Fan
H2020	Horizon 2020 = Acore 2020 = Vision 2020 goals
H2050	Horizon 2050 = Acore 2050 = Flight-path 2050 goals
HC	Hydrocarbon
HEP	Hybrid Electric Propulsion
IATA	International Air Transport Association
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organisation
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (https://www.ipcc.ch/)
ISO	Intermediate Stop Operation
JRC	Joint Research Centre, EC
LCA	Life Cycle Analysis
LCH4	Liquid Methane

LES	Large Eddy Simulation
LH2	Liquid Hydrogen
LII	Laser Induced Incandescence
LNG	Liquefied Natural Gas
LR	Long Range (aircraft)
LTO	Landing and Take-Off
MTOM	Maximum Take-Off Mass
MBM	Market Based Measures
MMU	Manchester Metropolitan University, UK
NAAQS	National Ambient Air Quality Standard
NAS	National Airspace System, USA
NAU	National Aviation University, Ukraine
NLF	Natural Laminar Flow
NLR	Netherlands Aerospace Centre
NO _x	Oxides of nitrogen (NO _x = NO ₂ + NO)
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
nvPM	non-volatile Particulate Matter
nvP#, nvPM#	non-volatile Particle (Matter) number
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
ON	ONERA
O ₃	Ozone
OPR	Overall Pressure Ratio
PEFC	Polymeric Electric Fuel Cells
PLIF	Planner Laser induced Incandescence
PM, PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀	Particulate Matter, PM of diameter less than 2.5 resp. 10 µm
PMTG	Particulate Matter Task Group, ICAO-CAEP
RDC	Rapid Dispersion Code
RR, RRD	Rolls-Royce, Rolls-Royce Deutschland
RF	Radiative Forcing
RTD	Research and Technology Development
RTF	Regional Turbo Fan
SAF	Sustainable Alternative Fuel
SAFRAN-AE	Safran Aircraft Engines
SESAR	Single European Sky ATM Research Programme

SID	Standard Instrument Departure
SLS	Sea Level Static
SMR	Short and Medium Range (aircraft)
SN	Smoke Number
SOA	Secondary Organic Aerosol
SO _x	Sulphur oxides
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
STAR	Standard Approach Routes
TE	Technology Evaluator, European Clean Sky programme
TRL	Technology Readiness Level (see appendix 3)
UFP	Ultrafine particles
UHC	Unburnt Hydrocarbon
UHBPR	Ultra High By-Pass ratio (Turbo Fan)
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
vPM	volatile Particulate Matter

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